

Hydride, Carbonyl and Hydrido Carbonyl Complexes of Platinum Group Metals—A Survey¹

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In the last two decades enormous number of hydride and carbonyl complexes of platinum metals have been characterised, and from time to time comprehensive reviews on the subject matter, especially on hydride complexes, have appeared²⁻¹⁰. The present survey is confined mostly to those complexes (polynuclear carbonyls are excluded) that have been reported in the recent past, say, the last 5-6 years.

In general, a majority of complexes containing hydridic hydrogen and/or carbon monoxide are diamagnetic implying that these ligands produce strong ligand-fields and favour spin-pairing. However, the two ligands are vastly different in the sense hydrogen cannot form π -bonds while with CO π -bonding is of primary importance. In spite of this both the ligands have a tendency to force the metal to conform to the 18 e or at least the 16 e rule. However, it is surprising to note that complexes containing only hydrogen and CO as ligands (carbonyl hydrides) are not very stable; but the metal-hydrogen and metal-CO bonds get stabilised when tertiary phosphines and/or arsines (or similar ligands), which are not only good π -acceptors but also fairly good σ -donors, are also present in the system. Hence, the stabilizing effect of tertiary phosphine and arsine ligands has been utilised in the synthesis of a wide range of hydride, carbonyl and hydrido carbonyl complexes.

This survey has been broadly divided into three parts:—(a) hydrides, (b) carbonyls and (c) hydrido carbonyls.

(a) Hydrides

Most of the properties of a hydride complex may be explained by visualising that the hydridic hydrogen acts as a negative ligand in the complex. It is found that the property of the hydridic hydrogen is markedly dependent on the nature of the metal atom to which it is attached and on the other ligands present in the com-

plex¹⁷. Hydride complexes containing a variety of ligands have been synthesised. There are also a few hydrides wherein hydridic hydrogen is the only ligand that is present.

The presence of hydride ligand may be detected by IR spectra. The hydridic hydrogen, however, is best detected by NMR spectra, and in several cases the nature of the multiplicity of the hydride resonance reveals the stereochemistry of the complex.

(i) Ruthenium and Osmium

A majority of the hydride complexes formed by Ru and Os are octahedral and have one hydridic hydrogen, though several containing more than one hydrogen are also known. In fact there are a few in which the number of hydridic hydrogens is as high as six, and in such complexes the metal has a high coordination number. All these complexes conform to the 18 e rule. Ru and Os also form several hydride complexes wherein the 18 e rule is not obeyed and consequently the coordination number is less than six (usually five).

The first report on the hydride complexes of these metals was published² as early as 1959, by Chatt and Hayter. Isolation of a four-coordinate hydride $[\text{HRuL}_2\text{BPh}_4]$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) has been claimed¹⁸. LiAlH_4 reduction of RuClCpL_3 in ether leads to the formation of HRuCpL_3 ($\nu_{\text{RuH}}=1950$; $\tau_{\text{H}}J_{\text{PH}}=21.73\text{t}/34$); this undergoes hydrogen insertion into the donor groups, like

List of Abbreviations: aq.=aqueous, acac=acetylacetonate, bipy=2,2'-bipyridyl, phen=1,10-phenanthroline, en=ethylene-diamine, pm=1,2-diaminopropane, Py=Pyridine, Pip=piperidine, Pic=picoline, Pyz=pyrazine, Izl=Imidazole, An=Aniline, p-tol= *p*-toluidine, azb=azobenzene, AcN=acrylonitrile, Cp=cyclopentadienyl, COD=1,5-cyclooctadiene, NBD=norbornadiene, Cot=cyclooctene, TCNE=tetracyanoethylene, FMN=fumaronitrile, *p*-tNC=*p*-tolyl isocyanide, DMA=NN'-dimethylacetamide, DMF=NN'-dimethylformamide, DMSO=dimethylsulphoxide, THF=tetrahydrofuran, MNTS=N-methyl N-nitrosotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide, dppe=1,2-bis(diphenyl phosphino) ethane, dae=1,2-bis(diphenyl arsino) ethane, dpp=1,3-bis(diphenyl phosphino) propane, vaa=*cis*-1,2-bis(diphenyl arsino) ethylene, ttp=PhP(CH₂CH₂CH₂PPH₂)₂, triphos=PhP(CH₂CH₂PPH₂)₃, tetraphos=Ph₂P(CH₂)₂P(Ph)(CH₂)₂P(Ph)(CH₂)₂PPH₂, P(CH₂CH₂PPH₂)₃, M=metals of the platinum group.

IR spectra: values are expressed as cm^{-1} (w=weak, m=medium, s=strong, m-s=medium to strong, vs=very strong, sh=shoulder).

UV & Visible spectra: values are expressed as nm.

NMR spectra: τ_{H} values are for metal bonded hydrogens (d=doublet, t=triplet, q=quartet, qn=quintet, dt=doublet of triplets, td=triplet of doublets, dqd=doublet of quartets further split into doublets, m=multiplet). Coupling constants (J) are in Hz (subscript -c=*cis* and t=*trans*).

fluoroacetylenes¹⁹. Hallman, McGarvey and Wilkinson²⁰ have reported the first five-coordinate hydride HRuXL_3 [X (ν $\text{RuH}/\lambda_{\text{max}}$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}$) = Cl (2020/470, 520; 27.44 q/26), Br (2025/530; 27.11 q/26)]²⁰⁻²². The hydride is obtained by several methods such as (a) by the action of H_2 (or aq. NaBH_4) on a benzene (or DMA) solution of RuX_2L_3 in presence of a base (Et_3N)^{20,21}, (b) by the reaction of ruthenium trichloride with PPh_3 and HCHO in methoxyethanol²², (c) by the photochemical (366 nm light) decarbonylation of $\text{HRuCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3$ in degassed benzene²³. The first method is also useful for the preparation of the dihydride H_2RuL_3 . X-ray studies²⁴ on HRuClL_3 ($\text{Ru-H} \sim 170\text{pm}$) indicate a highly distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with the phosphines in the axial positions; an *ortho* hydrogen of one of the phenyl groups occupies a place near the sixth coordination site. This violet black hydride is one of the most efficient hydrogenation catalysts known^{9,14,17,20-27}. James *et al*²⁷ suggest that in the stoichiometric hydrogenation of olefins with this hydride, the catalytically active species formed are HRuClL_2 . More recently, James, Rattray and Wang^{27a} have synthesised five-coordinate halide bridged hydride complexes of the type $[\text{HRuXL}_2]_2$ ($X = \text{Cl, Br; L} = \text{PPh}_3, \text{AsPh}_3$; ν $\text{RuH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = 2040-2100/22.5-23.7$), which are extremely sensitive toward O_2 and CO in solutions. They have also reported the formation of a five-coordinate Ru(III) hydride HRuBr_2L_2 ($\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3$; ν $\text{RuH}/\lambda_{\text{max}} = 2020/575$) by the substitution of bromide with hydrogen in RuBr_2L_2 : the four-coordinate hydride HRuBrL_2 has λ_{max} at 535 nm. Deprotonation of H_2RuL_4 ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) with $(\text{Ph}_3\text{C})\text{PF}_6$ yields the red complex $[\text{HRuL}_4]\text{PF}_6$ (nearly tetrahedral; ν $\text{RuH} = 2020$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}} = 18.02$ qn/20) which takes up solvent to form $[\text{HRu}(\text{MeCN})\text{L}_3]\text{PF}_6$ (ν $\text{RuH} = 1964$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}} = 23.7$ q/19)²⁸. The formation of 16 e cation $[\text{HRuL}_4]^+$ rather than an 18 e cation $[\text{HRuL}_5]^+$ has been attributed to the steric hindrance of the PPh_3 molecule. On the other hand, treatment of $[\text{HRuL}_4]\text{PF}_6$ with dichloromethane at 20°C or on heating a methanol solution of the acetate complex $\text{HRu}(\text{O}_2\text{CH}_3)\text{L}_3$ with HBF_4 precipitates a pale yellow hydride $[\text{HRuL}_3]\text{Y}$ ($\text{Y} = \text{BF}_4, \text{PF}_6$; ν $\text{RuH} = \text{PF}_6/2020$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}} = 18.75$ td/39.9)^{28,29}. X-ray structure determination of the resultant cation indicated an unusual coordination with one of the phenyl rings of one PPh_3 group bound as an arene to the metal; $\text{Ru-H} \sim 170$, $\text{Ru-C}(\text{Ph}) \sim 228$, and $\text{Ru-P} = 231.1, 233.2$ pm²⁹.

Wilson and Osborn³⁰ have prepared a series of penta-coordinate nitrosyl hydrides $\text{HM}(\text{NO})\text{L}_3[\text{M}(\text{L}) = \text{Ru}(\text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2, \text{PPr}^i\text{Ph}_2, \text{PCyPh}_2), \text{Os}(\text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2)]$ through the reductive elimination of halogen on refluxing EtOH-KOH (or methoxyethanol) solution of $\text{MCl}_3(\text{NO})\text{L}_2$ with excess L . X-ray crystal structure of $\text{HRu}(\text{NO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ shows a trigonal bipyramidal geometry with a linear nitrosyl group³¹. A five-coordinate hydride $\text{HRu}(\text{tri})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (tri = 1,3-diaryl triazenido ligand) has been reported by Laing, Robinson and Uttley³². Protonation of a methanol solution of $[\text{Ru}(\text{COD})\text{Cl}_2]_2$ in presence of N,N -dimethylhydrazine gives the cation $[\text{HRu}(\text{COD})(\text{NMe}_2\text{NH}_2)_3]^+$ (ν $\text{RuH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = 2000/12.87$) which loses hydrazine on treatment with donor molecules to yield penta-coordinate hydrides

$[\text{HRu}(\text{COD})\text{Q}]_2^+$ ($\text{Q} = \text{Py}, \gamma\text{-Pic}$) and hexa-coordinate hydrides $[\text{HRuL}_5]^+$ [$\text{L} = \text{P}(\text{OEt})_3, \text{P}(\text{OMe})_2\text{Ph}, \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$]¹⁸. Hydrogen cleavage, in the latter cation ($\text{L} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$) in alcohol, occurs on passing CO_2 to form $[\text{Ru}(\text{O}_2\text{COR})\text{L}_4]^+$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et}$) species³³.

The oxidative addition of HCl to $\text{RuCl}(\text{NO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) results in the formation of six-coordinate product $\text{HRuCl}_2(\text{NO})\text{L}_2$ ³⁴. Action of CO_2 on a benzene solution of $\text{H}_2\text{RuL}_4, \text{H}_2\text{Ru}(\text{N}_2)\text{L}_3$ or H_2RuL_3 produces the formate complex $\text{HRu}(\text{O}_2\text{CH})\text{L}_3$ (ν $\text{RuH} = 2010$)^{35,35}. The hydride has a distorted tetragonal pyramidal geometry as shown by the X-ray studies, and undergoes substitution reactions with $\text{N}_2, \text{H}_2, \text{HX}, \text{CO}, \text{PPh}_3$ as well as hydrogen insertion into CS_2 . Treatment of the formate complex $\text{HRu}(\text{O}_2\text{CH})\text{L}_3$ with alcohol gives $\text{HRu}(\text{O}_2\text{COR})\text{L}_3$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et}$)³⁵. A series of pale yellow airstable octahedral complexes of the composition $\text{HRu}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})\text{L}_3$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et, Pr}^n, \text{Pr}^i, \text{CF}_3, \text{Ph}, o\text{-tolyl}, p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ etc.) containing chelate carboxylate groups are isolated by prolonged reaction of RuCl_2L_3 with sodium carboxylate, and H_2 (or sodium hypophosphite) in boiling methanol^{36,37}. They are also obtained starting from H_2RuL_4 or $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and L .³⁷ The acetate complex ($\text{R} = \text{Me}$; ν $\text{RuH} = 2012/2016$; $\tau_{\text{H}} = 29.89$ q/28.6 q, $J_{\text{PH}} = 27$)^{36,37}, which is a powerful hydrogenation catalyst for terminal olefins, according to X-ray structure analysis has a distorted octahedral geometry ($\text{Ru-H} = 168$ pm)³⁸; the ESR spectrum of the powdered form at -150°C shows a weak signal at $g = 1.98$ with hyperfine splitting³⁸. Recently, this hydride has been found to be a good precursor in the preparation of a variety of cationic complexes³⁹. The Os analogs $\text{HOs}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})\text{L}_3$ [R/ν $\text{OsH}(\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}) = \text{Me}/2119(32.45\text{q}/21), \text{Et}/2124(32.4\text{q}/21)$] are obtained by the reaction of H_2OsL_3 with RCOOH in boiling methoxyethanol.³⁷ Chait and coworkers^{40,41} have isolated octahedral complexes of the form HOsClQL_3 [$\text{Q}(\text{L}) = \text{N}_2(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}, \text{PEt}_2\text{Ph}, \text{PETPh}_2), \text{PhNC}(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph})$] by treating OsCl_2QL_3 in alcohol with NaBH_4 . The isocyanide containing hydride (ν $\text{OsH} = 1930$) shows a doublet of triplets at 15.91 ($J_{\text{PH}} = 24, 83$) in the PMR spectrum⁴². A similar proton resonance splitting is obtained for the dinitrogen complexes suggesting the hydride ligand is *trans* to a P atom and *cis* to the other two P atoms which in turn are *trans* to one another⁴⁰. A series of cationic hydrides of the formula *trans*- $[\text{HM}(\text{Q})(\text{deph})_2]\text{BPh}_4$ ($\text{M} = \text{Ru, Os}$; $\text{Q} = \text{N}_2, \text{Me}_3\text{CNC, PhCN, CO}$ etc.) have been characterised by Bancroft *et al*⁴³.

The addition of neutral molecules (Q) to H_2RuL_3 takes place to give octahedral complexes H_2RuQL_3 ($\text{Q} = \text{N}_2, \text{NH}_3, \text{PhCN, CO}$; $\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3, p\text{-tolyl}, \text{P}^i\text{Ph}_3$). The dihydrides H_2RuL_4 ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2, \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}, \text{PET}_2\text{Ph}, p\text{-tolyl}_3\text{P}$) are prepared by different routes^{1,2,48,44}. Thus, a convenient synthesis of the PPh_3 complex (ν $\text{RuH} = 2080$; a tetrahedral arrangement of P ligands about Ru with hydride ligand situated on C_3 axis has been suggested) involves the NaBH_4 reduction of aq. RuCl_3 with excess PPh_3 in boiling ethanol²². The dihydride promotes C-O bond cleavage in vinyl or allyl carboxylates liberating ethylene

Scheme 2

Reversible oxidative addition of H_2 to H_2RuL_4 , $HRu(O_2CH)L_3$, $PhMe$ and $H_2Ru(N_2)L_3$ ($L = PPh_3$, p -tolyl $_3P$) in benzene occurs to form seven-coordinate tetrahydride H_4RuL_3 ⁵⁰. Ashworth and Singleton^{50a} have suggested the formation of seven-coordinate $Ru(IV)$ cationic trihydrides $[H_3Ru(L)_2]_2^+$ ($L = PMePh_2$; $L_2 =$ bidentate phosphine) as intermediates in the reaction of $[HRu(L)_2]_2^+$ with H_2 . Air-stable Os hydrides H_4OsL_3 [$L(\nu OsH) = PPh_3$ (2080w, 2020m, 1890s), PEt_2Ph (1984, 1885)] are isolated by the $NaBH_4$ reduction of Os salts or $OsCl_3L_3$ ($L = PEt_2Ph$, $AsEt_2Ph$, $AsPh_3$) with excess $L^{2,2,51}$. Similarly, $LiAlH_4$ reduction of $OsCl_3(PMe_2Ph)_2L$ ($L = PMe_2Ph$, PEt_2Ph , $AsMe_2Ph$) yields $H_4Os(PMe_2Ph)_2L$. The PMR spectra consist of a quartet resonance signal in the high field region suggesting fluxional behaviour for the tetrahydrides⁵¹. A preliminary report on the X-ray crystal structure of $H_4Os(PEt_2Ph)_3$ ($\tau_{H}/J_{PH} = 19.52q/9.4$) indicates a marked *trans* influence of the hydride ligands as seen from Os-P distances of 229.6 pm for mutually *trans* phosphines which are shorter than the Os-P bond length of 233.9 pm, presumably *trans* to a H ligand^{51a}. The PPh_3 complex reacts with CF_3COOH to give $HO(O_2CF_3)_3L_3$ ($\nu OsH = 2124w$)⁴⁷. Further, the tetrahydride ($L = PPh_3$) also substitutes H & L with chelating 1,3-diaryl triazenido (tri) ligand in methoxyethanol to form the trihydride $H_3Os(tri)L_2$ ($\tau_{H}/J_{PH} \sim 19t/13$)⁵². Isolation of a novel seven-coordinate hydrido complex containing dioxygen $HRuCl(O_2)$ ($AsMePh_3$)₃ ($\nu RuH/\nu OO = 1935/855$) has been claimed by Taqui Khan *et al*⁵³. The authors also claim to have synthesised a dinitrogen analog $HRuCl(N_2)$ ($AsPh_3$)₃ (air-stable, brown solid; $\nu RuH/\nu NN = 1950/2050$) by bubbling dinitrogen through a benzene-DMF solution of $HRuCl(AsPh_3)_3$.

Protonation of H_4OsL_3 ($L = PMe_2Ph$) gives an eight-coordinate pentahydrido cation $[H_5OsL_3]^+$, which shows only a singlet in the PMR spectrum due to H ligands indicating rapid intermolecular exchange⁵¹. $NaBH_4$ reduction of $OsCl_3L_3$ in boiling THF leads to the formation of the hexa-hydride H_6OsL_2 . The $AsEt_2Ph$ analog has also been prepared. These hydrides show a well-defined triplet [$L(\tau_{H}/J_{PH}) = PMe_2Ph$ (18.6/3.5), $AsEt_2Ph$ (19.6/33)] in the PMR spectra suggesting the equivalence of all the six hydrogens (integration of the signal confirmed the number of hydride ligands)^{51,52}.

(ii) Rhodium and Iridium

A large number of octahedral hydride complexes in addition to a few stable five-coordinate compounds of these metals have been well established. These compounds generally contain one hydride ligand in addition to other tertiary phosphine or arsine molecules. However, several di- and poly-hydrido complexes are also known. In some of these compounds the number of hydride ligands increases to as many as six, forcing the metal to have a higher oxidation state as well as coordination number. A majority of these complexes follow the 18e rule, but some of them conform to the 16e rule, and evidently, the latter complexes are coordinately unsaturated and easily undergo reactions involving addition and/or substitution.

Complexes of these metals represent by far the most numerous and thoroughly studied group of platinum metal hydrides, particularly those of Ir(III). They are, in general, very stable, and hence, their stereochemistries have been extensively investigated. Although the first hydrides of rhodium had been isolated as early as 1942 by Dwyer and Nyholm², they were erroneously formulated as compounds of Rh(II). Later, in the year 1960, these compounds were shown to be six-coordinate hydrides of the formula $HRhX_2$ ($AsMePh_2$)₃ ($X =$ halogen) by Lewis, Nyholm and Reddy². Perhaps the most extensive studies on hydrides of Ir were carried out by Chatt and Shaw and their coworkers.

Formation of hydrides with N_2 , $HRh(N_2)$ and $H_2Rh(N_2)$ has been claimed⁵⁴. Very recently, Hoffman *et al*^{55a} have found that the sodium amalgam reduction of $RhCl_3 \cdot 3H_2O$ in the presence of $PBu_3^tPh(L)$ in THF under dinitrogen atmosphere yields $HRh(N_2)L_3$ ($\nu RhH/\nu NN = 1977/2155$). Use of PCy_3 instead of PBu_3^tPh in the above system produces the dinitrogen bridged complex $[HRh(PCy_3)_2]_2N_2$. However, $HRh(N_2)L_2$ ($L = PCy_3$; $\nu NN = 2130$) has been obtained by reacting H_2RhL_2 with N_2 ; this hydride readily loses N_2 in solution. The crystal structure studies indicate a square-planar geometry for $HRh(N_2)$ (PBu_3^tPh)₃ with linear H-Rh-N-N arrangement (Rh-H = 166, Rh-P = 229.7, Rh-N = 197 and N-N = 107.4 pm). Protonation followed by ligand displacement of $RhCp(C_2H_4)_2$ with HY and L precipitates the four-coordinate cyclopentadienyl hydrides $[HRhCpL_2]Y$ ($L = PPh_3$; $Y = ClO_4, BF_4$)

from methanol⁵⁴. The first four-coordinate hydride of Rh, HRhL₃ ($\nu_{\text{RhH}}=2020$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=18.9$ d/13) obtained as an orange solid from RhCl₃ and AlPr₃⁴, was reported by Dewhirst *et al*⁵⁵. The Ir analog and HRh (AsPh₃)₃ are also known^{56,57}. NaBH₄ reduction of RhCl (tp) in ethanol yields HRh (tp); this is a good hydrogenation catalyst for 1-octene⁵⁸.

The five-coordinate hydride HRhL₄ (L=PPh₃), which is an efficient hydrogenation catalyst⁵⁹, is conveniently prepared by the NaBH₄ reduction of aq. RhCl₃ with excess L in boiling ethanol³². Displacement of L by PF₃ occurs to give HRhL₃(PF₃) ($\nu_{\text{RhH}}=2066$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=19.8$ dqd/199; $J_{\text{FH}}/J_{\text{RH}}=37/3.6$: an active hydrogenation and isomerisation catalyst for 1-octene⁶⁰ and HRhL₂(PF₃)₂ ($\nu_{\text{RhH}}=1986$). The Ir analog HIrL₄ (L/ $\nu_{\text{IrH}}=\text{PPh}_3/2245$, AsPh₃/2220) has been obtained by controlled potential electrolysis (using Hg electrode at room temperature) of HIrCl₃L₃ (Cosnf. I; X=Cl) in acetonitrile/benzene

with Et₄NClO₄ and excess L⁶¹. The deuterio complex DIr (PPh₃)₄ ($\nu_{\text{IrD}}=1610$) is prepared in the same way. In solution an equilibrium of the type HIrL₄ \rightleftharpoons HIrL₃ + L may be present.

Haszeldine, Parish and Parry⁶² have reported a series of air-stable hydrides HRhX(SiR₃)₂ (X = halogen; R = X, alkyl or aryl group; L = PPh₃, AsPh₃, SbPh₃) made by the oxidative addition of silanes, HSiR₃ to RhXL₃. The germanium analogs HRhCl(GeR₃)₂ (R = Cl, Me, Et L = PPh₃, AsPh₃) are also synthesised in a similar way. Rhodium trichloride or chlororidous acid reacts with bulky tertiary phosphines (L) in *iso*-propanol to yield five-coordinate hydrides HMCl₂L₂ which are shown to adopt a square-pyramidal configuration with H at the apex (Cl's are mutually *trans*) based on IR, NMR (τ_{H} is as high as 60) and X-ray struc-

ture results^{63,64}. A novel hydride HIr[PBu₂^t(C₆H₄O)]₂ ($\nu_{\text{IrH}}/\lambda_{\text{max}}=1995/535$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=57.77t/12.4$) is formed as dark purple crystals on refluxing an *iso*-propanol solution of iridium trichloride with PBu₂^t(C₆H₄OH-2)⁶⁵. This hydride, which is suggested to be square-pyramidal (P *trans* to P; H at the apex), is also

obtained by hydrogenating Ir[PBu₂^t(C₆H₄O)]₂ in benzene-*iso*-propanol. Moulton and Shaw⁶⁶ have also synthesised five-coordinate metallated hydrides of the type HMCl(PCP) ($\nu_{\text{RhCl}}/\tau_{\text{H}}=275s/37.5$; $J_{\text{RH}}/J_{\text{PH}}=52.8/12$; $\nu_{\text{IrCl}}/\nu_{\text{IrH}}=276s/2180$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=53/12$) by reacting aq. RhCl₃ or IrCl₃ with Bu₂^tPCH₂C₆H₄CH₂-PBu₂^t (PCPH) in refluxing propanol. Displacement of ad chloride with hydrogen in HRhCl₂L₂ (L = PBu₂^tMe) occurs to form the dihydride H₂RhClL₂⁶⁸. Huis and Masters^{66a}, recently have detected the formation of biheterometallic chloro-bridged hydrido complexes HRhCl(PBu^tPr₂)₂(μ -Cl)₂M'Cl' [M'/L' ($\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{RH}}/J_{\text{PH}}$) = Pd/PBu₃ (32.64/14.7/12.1), Pt/PEt₃ (32.67/14.7/11.8) Pt/PPr₂Bu^t (32.72/14.9/12.2), Pt/PBu₃ (32.68/15/12.1)] by reacting HRhCl₂ (PBu^tPr₂)₂ ($\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{RH}}/J_{\text{PH}}=41.16/35.6/13.2$) with M'₂Cl₂L'₂ in toluene.

Scheme 3

Isomeric (three forms) five-coordinate nitrosyl hydrido cations $[\text{HIr}(\text{NO})\text{L}_2\text{Y}]$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$; $\text{Y}=\text{ClO}_4$, BF_4 , PF_6) were prepared⁶⁷ by the oxidation of $\text{Ir}(\text{NO})\text{L}_3$ with HY . X-ray crystal structure determination suggests a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry (H being *trans* to NO and all the three P ligands occupying equatorial positions) for the black perchlorate compound ($\nu\text{IrH}=2150\text{m}$)⁶⁸; the brown isomer ($\nu\text{IrH}=2130\text{w}$) also adopts a similar configuration but with apical P atoms⁶⁹. The hydride ligand, in both the isomers, has not been located, however, Ir-N-O has been shown to be linear. Displacement of L with X (of LiX) occurs to give neutral hydride $\text{HirX}(\text{NO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}/\nu\text{IrH}=\text{Cl}/2080$), which with HX , further reacts to lose H, and forms (red) crystals of $\text{IrX}_2(\text{NO})\text{L}_2$. A five-coordinate nitrate hydride $\text{Hir}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{L}_2$ has also been characterised⁷⁰. Recently, Hawthorne and coworkers⁷¹⁻⁷³ have isolated a variety of new hydrido metal-carboranes of the form $\text{HM}(\text{carb})\text{L}_2(\text{carb}=\text{C}_2\text{B}_7\text{H}_9$, $\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}$; L=tertiary phosphine) by the oxidative addition of isomeric carbaboranes to MClL_3 in a suitable solvent like alcohol or ether. Likewise, oxidative addition of sulphurboranes, *closo*-1- $\text{SB}_n\text{H}_{n-1}$ ($n=9,11$) to IrCl_2 and RhCl_3 yields 2-(HirCl_2)-1- $\text{SB}_n\text{H}_{n-1}$ (trigonal bipyramidal; $n=9$; $\text{L}/\nu\text{IrH}=\text{PPh}_3/2199$, $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}=28.3\text{t}/14.7$; $\text{L}/\nu\text{IrH}=\text{AsPh}_3/2196$, $\tau_{\text{H}}=30.4$; $n=11$; $\text{L}/\nu\text{IrH}=\text{PPh}_3/2191$, $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}=27.3\text{t}/14.5$) and $\text{HRhL}_2(\text{SB}_{10}\text{H}_{10})$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{RhH}=\text{PPh}_3/2080$, $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}/\text{J}_{\text{RH}}=17.2/26/18$)^{73a}.

The β hydrides of Rh are readily converted to α form and the isomerisation ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$) proceeds more readily than for the corresponding Ir complexes, and is accelerated by light⁷⁷. Reactions of α & β hydrides of Rh(III) with several acids, bases, oxidants and reductants have been attempted. It is surprising to note that while the α hydrides of Rh, HRhX_2L_3 ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$; $\text{L}=\text{AsMePh}_2$, PEtPh_2) lose the hydride ligand to form $\text{Rh}(\text{HgY})\text{X}_2\text{L}_3$ ^{2,9,10}, the corresponding Ir(III) hydrides ($\text{L}=\text{PEt}_3$, PMe_2Ph , PEt_2Ph) give adducts of the type $\text{HirX}_2\text{L}_3 = \text{HgY}_2$ ($\text{Y}=\text{halogen}$) with mercuric halides⁷⁰. Brookes, Masters and Shaw⁸⁰ have investigated the photochemical isomerization reactions of octahedral Ir(III) complexes. The square-pyramidal hydrides HMCl_2L_2 undergo easy addition reactions with nucleophiles (Q) to yield six-coordinate hydrides $\text{HMCl}_2\text{L}_2\text{Q}$ ($\text{L}=\text{bulky phosphine ligand}$; $\text{Q}=\text{Py}$, MeNC , MeCN etc.). Details on the spectral studies of these complexes are reported^{64,81}. Duff and Shaw⁷⁸ have synthesised the phosphine metalated hydrides $\text{Hir}(\text{P-C})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PMe}_2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7$; $\text{P-C}=\text{PMe}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6^-)$; $\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{C}=\text{C}=2085/1547$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}=22.2\text{dt}/21.6$, 168_t) and $\text{Hir}(\text{P-C})_2\text{L}$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{C}=\text{C}=2010/1544$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}=19.2\text{dt}/21.6$, 144_t). On treatment with HCl , while the former undergoes demetallation to give HirCl_2L_2 ($\nu\text{IrH}=2270$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/\text{J}_{\text{PH}}=30.9\text{ dt}/21, 12$), the latter substitutes H with Cl. A mechanism involving hydrogen addition-elimination has been suggested for irridiation of phosphine.

There are now a large number of octahedral hydride complexes of stoichiometry HMx_2L_3 ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand; $\text{L}=\text{tertiary phosphine}$ or arsine) which have been well established; several of them isolated in two isomeric forms (α & β) have been assigned structures I and II, based on their IR and NMR results. In a few cases dipole moment measurements are also quite useful in ascertaining stereochemistry^{2-5,9-12,74-78}.

Oxidative addition of carboxylic acids (RCOOH) to the dinitrogen complex $\text{IrCl}(\text{N}_2)_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) leads to the formation of octahedral carboxylato complex $\text{HirCl}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{alkyl, aryl}$) which with CO forms a hydrido carbonyl $\text{HirCl}(\text{CO})(\text{O}_2\text{CR})\text{L}_2$ ⁸². Deeming and Shaw⁸³ have suggested that the equilibrium constant for the reaction of sterically non-hindered carboxylic acids with $\text{IrX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ to give $\text{HirX}(\text{O}_2\text{CR})\text{L}_2$

increases with increasing pK_a of the acid. The dinitrogen complex also reacts with aromatic azo or imine compounds PhX=NR(X=N, CH; R=alkyl, aryl) and 2-(methyl azo) propene, H₂C=CMe-N=NMe to produce metallated hydrides HIr(C₆H₄X=NR)ClL₂ and HIr(CH=CMe-N=NMe)ClL₂ respectively, which show a diagnostic νIrH band around 2100 cm⁻¹ in the infrared and a triplet resonance in the high field region (τ_H/J_{PH}=24.30/~17) of the PMR spectra^{8,4}. Addition of X₂ to HIrX(PhC=CHCH=NPr)L₂ (X=Cl, Br; L=PCy₃) yields substituted products HIrX(PhC=CXCH=NPr)L₂ without rupture of the Ir-C bonds. Treatment of HIrCl(SMeC₆H₃CH=NMe)L₂ (L=PPh₃) with AgClO₄ followed by Q (CyNC, CO leads to the formation of complexes [Hir(SMeC₆H₃CH=NMe)QL₂]ClO₄, the metallocyclic ring remaining intact^{9,4a}.

p-tolyl; νIrH/τ_H~2275/23.5)^{9,0}. Meek and coworkers^{91,92} have isolated cationic hydrides [HRhCl(S)(ttP)]BF₄ [S(νRhH/τ_H)=MeCN(2180 w/24.6m), EtOH (-/26.1 m)] containing tridentate phosphine, by protonating RhCl(ttP) with HBF₄·Et₂O in ethanol. Oxidative addition of HCl and H₂ to RhCl(ttP) in dichloromethane yields HRhCl₂(ttP) (νRhH=2193) and H₂RhCl(ttP) (νRhH=2195 w) respectively.

Oxidative addition of HX or H₂ to square-planar species [Rh(L-L)₂]⁺ gives octahedral hydrido cations [HRhX(L-L)₂]⁺ and [H₂Rh(L-L)₂]⁺ (X=Cl, Br; L-L=bidentate phosphine or arsine) respectively^{93,94}. Dihydrido cations [H₂RhL₂]⁺ (L=PMe₃, PEt₃, PBu₃, PhEt₂) are also known^{95,96}. A variety of dihydrido cations [H₂Rh(S)₂L₂]⁺ (L=PPh₃, PCyPh₂; S=MeCN,

Scheme 6

An extensive series of cationic amine hydrides *trans*-[HRhQ(N-N)]²⁺ (Q=NH₃, H₂O; N-N=en, pn) have been well characterised by Wilkinson and coworkers^{85,86}. Recently, Nanje Gowda and Reddy⁸⁷ have carried out substitution reactions of α and β hydrides of Rh(III), HRhX₂L₂ with potential bidentate nitrogen bases bipy and phen, and have isolated a wide range of cationic complexes [HRhX(N-N)L₂]ClO₄ (X=Cl, Br; N-N=bipy, phen; L=PEtPh₂, AsMePh₂, AsEtPh₂, AsPrPh₂) and [RhX₂(N-N)L₂]ClO₄. IR and NMR data have been invaluable in assigning structures to the cations (L *trans* to L). A facile oxidative addition of HX to cations [Ir(COD/NBD)(N-N)]⁺ produces octahedral hydrides [HirX(COD/NBD)(N-N)]⁺ (X=halogen; H *trans* to X)⁸⁸. Oxidative addition of H₂ to [Ir(COD)L₂]PF₆ (L=PMePh₂, PBu₃⁺, PPh₃) in CD₂Cl₂ (-80°C) yields *cis*-[H₂Ir(COD)L₂]PF₆ (L=PMePh₂; τ_H/J_{PH}=19.8 dd/20.0, 90₄; H *trans* to L; τ_H/J_{PH}=23.7 dd/16; H *trans* to COD)^{88,4}. Reaction of [IrCl(Cot)₂]₂ with a bidentate hybrid ligand PN (o-Me₂NC₆H₄PPh₂) in presence of NH₄PF₆ gives [HirCl(PN)₂]PF₆ (νIrH/νIrD=2240/1604; τ_H/J_{PH}=32/8)⁸⁹. The cyclooctene complex [IrCl(Cot)₂]₂ also reacts with arenethiols and tertiary phosphines in benzene to yield [HirCl(SAr)(PR₃)₂]₂, which with chlorinated solvents further reacts to form [H₂Ir₂Cl(SAr)₂(PR₃)₄]Cl·H₂O (Ar=Ph, *p*-tolyl, etc; R=Ph,

Me₂CO, EtOH) and [H₂RhbipyL₂]⁺ (L=PMe₃Ph, PMePh₂, PCyPh₂, PPh₃, AsPh₃) are formed on hydrogenation of [Rh(NBD)L₂]⁺ in polar medium (S) and ether (and bipy, for the latter compounds)^{97,98}. These hydrides are shown to be potential catalysts for several organic reaction systems, and comparable to Wilkinson's catalyst in activity. The high field PMR spectra of the solvent coordinated hydrides consist of a doublet of triplets suggesting a structure with *trans* phosphines and *cis* hydrogens. An Ir analog [H₂Ir(Me₂CO)₂(PPh₃)₂]⁺ is also known⁹⁸.

On refluxing a piperidine solution of (NH₄)₂IrX₆, cationic hydrides *trans*-[HirX(Pip)₄]⁺ (X=halogen) are obtained⁹⁹. Displacement of chloride with the anionic ligand of KY (Y=NCO, NCS, NCSe) in aq. medium occurs to form *trans* [HirY(Pip)₄]Y which (Y=NCS; νIrH/νCN(N-bound)=2215/2090) further reacts with NaBPh₄ in dichloromethane to give *trans*-[Hir(SCN)(Pip)₄]BPh₄ (νIrH/νCN(S-bound)=2215/2104). A study on the mode of thiocyanate bonding in these complexes has been attempted¹⁰⁰.

Shaw and S'ade¹⁰¹ have reported the formation of octahedral hydrido dications [HirQ₂(PMe₂Ph)₂]²⁺ (Q=Py, phen/2); the Py complex has the spectral para-

meters $\nu\text{IrH}=2205$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=30.15/19.2, 13.5$. Structures for the dications with hydride being *cis* to all the three phosphines and *trans* to a nitrogen ligand, have been suggested. Oxidation of $[\text{Ir}(\text{MeNC})(\text{dppe})_2]^+$ with HCl produces $[\text{HIr}(\text{MeNC})(\text{dppe})_2]^+(\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=20.7\text{dt}/10.2, 117.4)^{103}$. Protonation of the cationic compounds $[\text{M}(\text{RNC})_3\text{L}_2]\text{PF}_6$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) in acetone with HPF_6 forms the octahedral hydrido dications $[\text{HM}(\text{RNC})_3\text{L}_2]^{2+}$ [$\text{M}(\text{R})=\text{Rh}(\text{Bu}^t)$, $\text{Ir}(\text{Bu}^t)$, $p\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4$, $p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$] as white crystals. The ^1H NMR spectra of Ir complexes show a triplet ($\tau_{\text{H}}=17\text{-}21$) indicating the hydride *trans* to RNC, and *cis* to two mutually *cis* or *trans* phosphines¹⁰³. Addition of an isocyanide to the trihydride H_3IrL_2 ($\text{L}=\text{AsPh}_3$), gives the six-coordinate hydride $\text{H}_3\text{Ir}(\text{RNC})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{Et}$, Cy , *p*-tolyl *p*-anisyl) in which a hydride ligand can be cleaved by an acid HX ($\text{X}=\text{F}$, Cl , Br , N_3) to form the dihydride $\text{H}_2\text{IrX}(\text{RNC})\text{L}_2$ ¹⁰⁴. The trihydride $\text{H}_3\text{Ir}(p\text{-tNC})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CN}=2080, 2060/2120$) further reacts with carboxylic acids (RCOOH) in ethanol to give a mixture of the paramagnetic complex $\text{Ir}(\text{O}_2\text{CC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}p)_2(p\text{-tNC})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{CN}=2135$; $\mu_{\text{eff}}=1.67$ B.M.; ESR data: $g_{11}/g_1=2.04/2.02$) and the trihydride H_3IrL_2 ¹⁰⁵. The latter trihydride ($\text{L}=\text{PET}_3$, PET_2Ph , PMePh_2 , PETPh_2 , PPh_3 , AsEt_2Ph) has been isolated in two isomeric forms^{106, 107}. X-ray crystal structure determination for the PPh_3 hydride suggests a meridional distorted octahedral configuration with Ir-H bond lengths 158 and 162 pm for mutually *trans* hydride ligands; the hydride *trans* to P lies at a distance of 159 pm from Ir atom¹⁰⁸.

Although Chatt *et al* and Malatesta *et al* were the first to synthesise the seven-coordinate penta-hydrides of Ir(V), they were erroneously formulated as trihydrides H_3IrL_2 ^{10, 12}. Later, these have been reformulated as H_5IrL_2 ($\text{L}=\text{tertiary phosphine}$) based on ^1H and ^{81}P NMR studies^{92, 109}, and act as homogeneous hydrogenation catalysts for hydrogen transfer involving mono-olefins¹¹⁰. $\text{H}_5\text{Ir}(\text{PPr}_3)_2$ has the spectral parameters, $\nu\text{IrH}/\delta\text{IrH}=1950/875$, $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=20.8/11$. Displacement of H_2 in $\text{H}_5\text{Ir}(\text{PET}_2\text{Ph})_2$ by nucleophiles (PPh_3 , AsMe_2Ph , SbPh_3 , MeNC , CO etc) has also been observed¹⁰⁹.

Reaction of LiH with metallic Rh at 600°C in an inert atmosphere produces products of the composition Li_4RhH_4 and Li_5RhH_5 , which are weakly paramagnetic, have Rh-H bond distances 181-196 pm as shown by X-ray analysis¹¹¹. More recently, polyhydrido compounds $\text{H}_8\text{Rh}(\text{CoB})_{10}$ and $\text{H}_{15}\text{Rh}(\text{Ni}_2\text{B})_{10}$ (pyrophoric), which are active hydrogenation catalysts, have been obtained by the NaBH_4 reduction of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with $\text{CoCl}_2/\text{NiCl}_2$ in ethanol¹¹². In addition to these, several polynuclear bridged hydrido compounds have been made. White, Liver and Maitlis¹¹³ have isolated a wide range of dinuclear bridged hydrides HM_2Cl_3 (C_5Me_5)₂, $[\text{HM}_2\text{X}_2(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2]^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{M}_2(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2]^+$ ($\text{X}=\text{CH}_3\text{CO}_2$, CF_3CO_2) and $[\text{H}_3\text{Ir}_2(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2]^+$. IR and NMR studies are very helpful in assigning stereochemistry of the compounds. The complex HRh_2Cl_3 (C_5Me_5)₂ has a triplet at 21.54 τ ($J_{\text{RH}}=23$) in the PMR spectrum and νRHRH band at 1151 cm^{-1} in the infrared. It acts as a homogeneous hydrogenation catalyst, and crystal structure studies have located the

bridged hydride ligand at a distance of 184.9 pm from Rh atom¹¹⁴.

(iii) Palladium and Platinum

These metals form diamagnetic hydride complexes, the majority of which have a square-planar geometry and obey the 16e rule rather than the 18e rule. Further, although the compounds having 16e configuration are coordinately unsaturated, it appears that they do not show high tendency towards nucleophilic addition to attain the 18e configuration. The Pt hydrides seem to be more prone towards oxidative addition reactions than Pd compounds, and some octahedral hydrido complexes of Pt(IV) have been isolated.

Among the platinum group metal hydrides, report on the hydride complexes of Pt appears to be the earliest, and the complexes were recognised as early as 1957 by Chatt, Duncanson and Shaw². Since then, there have been several reports on the synthesis of Pt hydrides *trans*- HPtXL_2 ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand; $\text{L}=\text{tertiary phosphine}$ or arsine) by various methods⁹⁻¹⁵. The hydrides *trans*- HPtClL_2 [$(\nu\text{PtH}/\tau_{\text{H}}; J_{\text{PH}}/J_{\text{PtH}})=\text{PPr}_3$ (2193/28.55 t; 12.6/1285), PCy_2Ph (2223/28.21 t; 12.5/1250), PCy_3 (2172/28.81 t; 12.7/1282)]¹¹⁵, which ($\text{L}=\text{PPr}_3$, PMe_2Ph) act as remarkable catalysts for butadiene oligomerization and olefin isomerization¹¹⁶, are obtained by hydrazine hydrate reduction of PtCl_2L_2 in refluxing methoxy:thanol, except the PCy_3 complex, which is obtained by other routes^{115, 117}.

NaBH_4 reduction of $\text{Pt}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{PPh}_2)_2$ in benzene-ethanol produces $\text{HPt}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{PPh}_2)(\text{PPh}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}))$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{OH}=2220/2500$, 2415; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}/J_{\text{PtH}}=29.22\text{dd}/13.43$, 17.09/1205)¹¹⁸. Oxidative addition of HSiR_3 to $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{L}_2$ occurs to form *cis*- $\text{HPt}(\text{SiR}_3)_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{alkyl}$, aryl; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$; $\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{SiH}=2055\text{-}2144/2105\text{-}2194$)¹¹⁹. The hydrides *cis*- HPtClL_2 and $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_2\text{L}_2$ which were reported earlier, are shown to be different crystallographic modifications of *trans*- HPtClL_2 , based on IR and NMR evidences¹²⁰. Reaction of dithiophosphinic acids, R_2PSSH with PtL_4 leads to the formation of $\text{HPt}(\text{SSPR}_2)_2$ ($\text{R}/\nu\text{PtH}=\text{Ph}/2148\text{m}$, $\text{PhO}/2165\text{m-s}$)¹²¹. Areneselenenols, RSeH also oxidise PtL_4 to *cis/trans*- $\text{HPt}(\text{SeR})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{Ph}$, *p*-tolyl; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, PMePh_2)¹²². Roundhill and coworkers¹²³ find that the protonation of $\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{L}_2$ or PtL_4 ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) with fluorocarboxylic acids yields hydrido cations $[\text{HPtL}_2]^+$ and $[\text{HPtL}_3]^+$. The latter hydrido cations, where $\text{L}=\text{PMePh}_2$, PMe_2Ph , PET_3 , AsEt_3 , are also known^{124, 125}. ^1H and ^{81}P NMR studies have been attempted¹²⁶ for the cationic species $[\text{HPtL}_2]^+$ ($\text{L}=\text{PET}_3$, PPh_3) and *trans*- $[\text{HPt}(\text{PET}_3)_2(\text{PPh}_3)]^+$. The two independent spectral parameters for the hydrido cation $[\text{HPt}(\text{PET}_3)_3]^+$, are $\nu\text{PtH}/\tau_{\text{H}}=2090/16.4$ dt and 2126/15.9 dt ($J_{\text{PtH}}/J_{\text{PH}}=788/15.0$, 157 t)^{124, 127}. PtL_4 ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, AsPh_3) on treatment with succinimide or maleimide, gets oxidised to afford the hydrido-imido complex $\text{HPt}(\text{imide})\text{L}_2$ ¹²⁸.

Although Pt forms an extensive series of fairly stable hydrides HPtXL_2 , the corresponding Pd complexes are much less stable. This might lead to the conclusion that the Pd-H bond in these complexes appears to be

Scheme 7

not very stable. Despite this, a series of four-coordinate hydrides HPdXL_2 ($\text{X} = \text{halogen, anionic ligand}$; $\text{L} = \text{PPr}_3^t, \text{PCy}_3, \text{PPh}_3$; $\nu\text{PdH}/\tau_{\text{H}} \sim 2030/24t$) have been synthesised by Green *et al*¹²⁹ and Kudo *et al*¹³⁰. These are thermally quite stable, and the Pd-H bond in these is presumably stabilised by the bulky phosphines. The crystal structure of the square-planar complex *trans*- $\text{HPdCl}(\text{PEt}_3)_2$ has been determined ($\text{Pd-Cl} = 242.7$; $\text{Pd-P} = 231, 230.6$ pm), without locating the hydride ligand^{130a}. The bidentate phosphine, *dppe*, will substitute X and L in HPdXL_2 in presence of NH_4PF_6 in benzene-methanol to give cationic species $[\text{HPd}(\text{dppe})\text{L}]\text{PF}_6$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPr}_3^t, \text{PCy}_3$)¹³¹. PdL_2 adds on H_2 and CF_3COOH , oxidatively, to yield polymeric hydride ($\nu\text{PdH}/\delta\text{PdH} = 2260/847$) and *trans*- $\text{HPd}(\text{O}_2\text{CCF}_3)_2$ [$\nu\text{PdH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = \text{PBu}_3^t$ (2202/28.27), $\text{PBu}_3^t \text{Ph}$ (2190/27.17)] respectively¹³². NaBH_4 reduction of $\text{Pd}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PCy}_3$) yields

Adlard and Socrates¹³⁴ have investigated the influence of solvents on the bonding mode of thiocyanate ligand in *trans*- $\text{HPt}(\text{SCN})_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PBu}_3^t, \text{AsBu}_3^t$) by employing PMR spectroscopy, Air-stable linkage isomers $\text{HPt}(\text{CNBPh}_3/\text{NCBPh}_3)_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PEt}_3$) synthesised by different routes, were characterised by IR,¹³⁵ and ¹³B NMR studies¹³⁶. The hydride *trans*- $\text{HPt}(\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh})_2$ got in the reaction of HPtCl_2 with $\text{NaC}\equiv\text{CPh}$ in benzene, substitutes the hydride ligand with dimethyl acetylene carboxylate to give *trans*- $\text{Pt}\{\text{HC}(\text{CO}_2\text{Me})=\text{C}(\text{CO}_2\text{Me})\}(\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh})_2$.¹³⁷ Addition of Lewis acids ($\text{Q} = \text{AlCl}_3, \text{AlMe}_3, \text{CoCl}_2, \text{ZnCl}_2, \text{NiCl}_2$ etc) to *trans*- HPtCNL_2 takes place to afford *trans*- $\text{HPtCNL}_2\text{Q}^{137}$. Ebsworth *et al*^{137a} have investigated the reactions of silyl and germyl derivatives with HPtXL_2 ($\text{X} = \text{halogen}$; $\text{L} = \text{PEt}_3$). Reaction of *trans*- HPtCl_2 with silanethiol, SiH_3 (SH) yields *trans*- $\text{HPt}(\text{SH})_2$ ($\tau_{\text{H}} = 20.08$).

Scheme 8

$\text{HPd}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{L}_2$. Substitution of nitrate with solvent ($\text{S} = \text{Me}_2\text{CO, MeOH}$) in presence of NaBPh_4 occurs to give $[\text{HPd}(\text{S})_2]\text{BPh}_4$, which undergoes displacement of solvent molecule with neutral molecules ($\text{Q} = \text{Py}$, substituted Py , Pyz , Iz1) to form $[\text{HPdQL}_2]^+$ ($\nu\text{PdH} = 1000-2075$).^{132a} The formation of an unstable hydride *trans*- $\text{HPd}(\text{CCl} = \text{CCl}_2)_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) in the reaction of $\text{PdCl}(\text{CCl} = \text{CCl}_2)_2$ with NaOMe , has been detected by Otsuka and coworkers¹³³. The low νPdH (1856) and τ_{H} (17.62) values for this hydride, have been attributed to the high *trans* influence of the ligand *trans* to H and enhanced d-shielding of the proton. This is apparent for the hydrides *trans*- $\text{HPt}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = 1920/14.64$) and $\text{H}_2\text{Pt}(\text{PBu}_3^t\text{Ph})_2$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = 1740/13.05$).

An easy displacement of chloride in *trans*- HPtCl_2 ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) occurs on treatment with a methanol solution of AgClO_4 to form the perchlorate coordinated hydride $\text{HPt}(\text{OClO}_3)_2$, which with neutral molecules (Q) further undergoes substitution reactions giving hydrido cations *trans*- $[\text{HPtQL}_2]^+$ [$\text{Q} = \text{Py}$; $\text{NH}_3, \text{MeNH}_2, \text{C}_2\text{H}_4, \text{C}_2\text{H}_6, \text{PPh}_3, \text{SbPh}_3, \text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$]¹³⁸. The hydride analogs are also obtained by the displacement of halide in *trans*- HPtXL_2 with nucleophiles^{134, 139, 140}. Solvent bound cationic hydrides *trans*- $[\text{HPt}(\text{S})_2]\text{BPh}_4$ [$\nu\text{PtH}/\delta\text{PtH} = \text{PPh}_3/\text{DMF}$ (2038/834m), $\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2060m/-)] have also been characterised¹⁴¹. The hydride ligand in *trans*- $[\text{HPt}(\text{Me}_2\text{CO})_2]^+$ ($\text{L} = \text{PEt}_3$) inserts into C_2H_4 to form *trans*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)(\text{Me}_2\text{CO})_2]^+$ which on

Scheme 9

treatment with LiCl gives *trans*-PtCl(C₂A₈)L₂. Kinetics and mechanism of hydride insertion have been described¹⁴². The reaction of lithium carbaboranes and isocyanides with *trans*-HPtClL₂ in ether produces *cis/trans*-HPt(σ-carb)L₂ (σ-carb = 1,2- and 1,7-B₁₀C₂H₁₁⁻, 7-Me-1,7-B₁₀C₂H₁₀⁻ etc.) and *trans*-[HPt(RNC)L₂]Cl respectively; the latter complex undergoes ready hydride insertion into isocyanide to give PtCl(CHNR)L₂¹⁴³⁻¹⁴⁵. The cationic hydrides [HPt(RNC)L₂]ClO₄ (R = Me, Ph, *p*-NO₂C₆H₄) react with amines HNR'R'' (R' = H, Me; R'' = Me, Et, Ph, *p*-MeC₆H₄) to yield carbene complexes *trans*-[HPt(C(NHR)NR'R'')L₂]ClO₄ which with strong bases (e.g., KOH) undergo deprotonation to give amidino hydrides *trans*-HPt{C(NR')R''}L₂¹⁴⁶. Investigation on the kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of methyl acrylate (Ol) with *trans*-HPt(NO₃)L₂ has revealed the evidence for the intermediate [HPt(Ol)L₂]⁺ species¹⁴⁷. X-ray study on the complex *trans*-HPt(*p*-MeC₆H₄N₃C₃H₄Me-*p*(PPh₃)₂) has been made [Pt-P=226.7 & 226.8, Pt-N=209 & 281 pm; νPtH/τH=2143/24.2t]^{147a}.

Dihydrido complexes *trans*-H₂PtL₂ [L(νPtH/τH=PCy₃(1720/13.06t), PEtCy₂(1925/15.6t), PPtCy₂(1920/16.9t), PCy₂Ph(1765/13.18t; νPtD=1270s), PPt₂(1723/14.01t)] and *trans*-H₂Pd(PCy₃)₂ (νPdH=1740) are isolated by stirring a mixture of M(acac)₂, L and AlEt₃ in ether at 60°C, or by the LiBH₄ reduction of PtCl₂(AsPh₃)₂ in presence of excess L^{148,150}. Moulton and Shaw¹⁴⁸ have described the first example of a *cis* dihydride of Pt(II) H₂Pt(Bu₂PCH₂C₆H₄CH₂PBu₂)₂ (τH/νPtH/νPtD=14.00/1008/22.2, 165t) obtained by the NaBH₄ reduction of PtCl₂(Bu₂CN)₂ in ethanol and in presence of P-P (Bu₂PCH₂C₆H₄CH₂PBu₂). This hydride reacts with HCl in ether to produce *cis*-HPtCl(P-P) (νPtH/νPtCl=2085s/282s). One of the hydride ligands in *trans*-H₂PtL₂ (L=PCy₃) can be easily cleaved or inserted into the donor group, by reacting with CCl₄ and CS₂ (under N₂ atmosphere) respectively to give the monohydrides *trans*-HPtYL₂ [Y(νPtH/τH; νPtH/νPtD)=Cl(2150/26.5t; 14'1200), S₂CH(2130/22.58t; 13'1280)]¹⁴⁹. X-ray structure of the CS₂ inserted complex has been attempted. Action of H₂ and HM'R₃ (M'/R=Ge/Me, Si/Et) on Pt(C₂H₄)₂L (L=PCy₃) pro-

Scheme 10

duces a new class of hydride-bridged complexes $H_2Pt_2L_2$ [$\nu PtH(\text{terminal})/\nu PtH(\text{bridged})=2090/1550$; $PtD(\text{terminal})=1490$] and $H_2Pt_2(M'R_3)_2L_2$ respectively. Crystal structure of the latter silyl complex has been determined; hydride ligands have not been located. They hydrido complexes have been found to serve as hydrosilation and hydrogermylation catalysts¹⁵⁰.

The oxidation of PtL_4 ($L=PPh_3$) with $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ in ethanol leads to the formation of six-coordinate $Pt(IV)$ hydride $HPtCl(SnCl_3)(OEt)L_2$ ($\nu PtH=2130$)¹⁵¹. Anderson, Ebsworth and Rankin¹⁵¹ have described the synthesis of octahedral hydrides $HPtX_3L_2$ and $H_2PtX_2L_2$ ($X=\text{halogen}$; $L=PPh_3$) by the oxidative addition of HX to PtX_2L_2 and $HPtXL_2$ respectively. These workers have correlated the magnitude of the coupling constants J_{PtH} , J_{PtL} and J_{PL} , which decrease from (the corresponding) four- to six-coordinate hydrides, with the covalency (which decreases) in the Pt-H bond. They have also reported the hydrides $HPt(GeR_3)L_2$ ($R_3=H_2Cl, HCl_2$) containing germyl groups. Configurations for these hydrides are assigned based on the results from NMR spectra. Six-coordinate hydrides of $Pt(IV)$, $HPtL_2(SiH_2I)L_2$ and $H_2Pt(C_6H_4O)_2L_2$ have also been reported¹⁵¹⁻¹⁵³.

(b) Carbonyls

Carbon monoxide—the most important π -acceptor ligand—possess vacant π -orbitals in addition to lone pair of electrons. These vacant orbitals accept electron density from the filled metal orbitals to form π -bonding that supplements the σ -bonding arising from lone pair donation. A large number of the carbonyl complexes of platinum metals conform to the 18e rule and are usually diamagnetic. However, the majority of $Rh(I)$, $Ir(I)$ and $Pt(II)$ compounds obey the 16e rule. Because of the high ligand-field strength of CO, the metal atom in a complex will be forced into a low-spin state (which leads to diamagnetism). Another important property of CO, which arises due to its high π -acceptor capacity, is its ability to stabilise a metal complex wherein the metal is in a low oxidation state.

Infrared spectroscopy is the most useful tool to detect the existence of CO in a complex. Diagnostic carbonyl stretch (νCO) for free CO (gas) occurs at 2143 cm^{-1} whereas the corresponding frequencies for coordinated carbonyl groups, MCO ($M=\text{metal}$), appear at lower frequencies ($1900\text{--}2100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for terminal and $1730\text{--}1940\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for bridging groups). The νCO depends on the CO bond order which in turn reflects the MC bond order. An additional factor influencing the CO bond order is the charge on the metal atom. νCO decreases with increase in atomic number in any vertical column (or horizontal row) of the periodic table, but increases as the oxidation state of the metal is enhanced (or the electron density on the metal atom is reduced). In the lower oxidation state $d\pi\text{--}p\pi$ bonding will lead to a higher M-C bond order and a lower νCO . X-ray studies indicate that the C-O bond length will be normally little higher for the coordinated than for the free ligand (112.8 pm)¹⁵⁴.

(i) Ruthenium and Osmium

Numerous octahedral mono and dicarbonyl complexes are known for these metals. It is observed that a majority of these have the metal in the +2 oxidation state, and investigations have been done more on Ru rather than Os complexes. A few carbonyl complexes with $M(O)$ and $M(III)$ oxidation states have also been reported.

CO displaces the chloride ligand in $RuClCpL_2$ ($L=PPh_3$) to give four-coordinate carbonyl $[Ru(CO)CpL_2]^+$ species¹⁵⁵. Treatment of $HRuCl(CO)L_3$ with MNTS in presence of LiX ($X=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand) leads to the formation of a five-coordinate nitrosyl carbonyl $RuX(CO)(NO)L_2$ ¹⁵⁶. The Os analog is also known¹⁵⁷. Cleavage of the chloride group in $OsCl(CO)(NO)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3, PCy_3$) occurs on treatment with an acetone solution of $AgPF_6$ to yield $[Os(CO)(NO)L_2]PF_6$ or $[Os(CO)(NO)(Me_2CO)L_2]PF_6$ ¹⁵⁸. These carbonyls undergo addition or substitution (of Me_2CO) reactions with nucleophiles to form five-coordinate cationic complexes $[Os(CO)(NO)QL_2]PF_6$ [$Q=CO,$

Scheme 11

PR₃, C₂H₂, C₂Ph₂, C₂(CO₂Me)₂, C₂H₄]. The ethylene complex is thought to possess a trigonal bipyramidal geometry with CO, NO and C₂H₄ in the equatorial positions; the ¹³C NMR data provides a direct evidence for the rotation of C₂H₄ through metal-olefin bond. The dicarbonyl cation [Os(CO)₂(NO)L₂]⁺ (L=PPh₃; νCO/νNO=2055,2000/1750) is also obtained by deprotonating HOs(CO)(NO)L₂ with non coordinating acids, HY (Y=ClO₄, BF₄, PF₆) in presence of CO¹⁵⁹. A trigonal bipyramidal configuration with PPh₃ groups occupying axial positions (N-O linear) is indicated, by X-ray analysis, for the cation. Nucleophiles substitute a CO molecule in the dicarbonyl to form [Os(CO)(NO)QL₂]⁺ [Q(νCO/νNO)=PPh₃ (1950/1705), dppe (1960/1700), *p*-tNC (νCN=2150)]. With excess *p*-tNC and in presence of dioxygen, the dicarbonyl cation yields a six-coordinate nitrito carbonyl cation [Os(CO)(NO₂)(*p*-tNC)₂L₂]⁺ (νCO/νCN=2050/2200, 2160; νNO₂=1310, 1380)¹⁵⁹. Deprotonation of [HRu(CO)(*p*-tNC)QL₂]⁺ (L=PPh₃; Q=CO, L) with sodium hydroxide (in the absence of O₂) yields Ru(CO)₂(*p*-tNC)L₂ (νCO/νCN=1999, 1865/2062, 2042) and Ru(CO)(*p*-tNC)L₂ (νCO/νCN=1901/2090), while in presence of O₂, the cation (Q=L) affords Ru(CO)(*p*-tNC)(O₂)L₂ (νCO/νCN=1920/2115; νOO=838)¹⁶⁰.

A simple five-coordinate carbonyl RuCl₂(CO)L₂ (L=PCy₃; νRuCl/νCO=335/1930) is isolated as an orange solid, by the addition of PCy₃ to the red carbonyl solution of aq. RuCl₃ in methoxyethanol. The complex, having a square-pyramidal configuration (with CO at the apex, and mutual *trans* Cl's and *trans* PCy₃'s in the square plane), takes up a molecule of CO to the unoccupied octahedral site giving *cis* and *trans*-RuCl₂(CO)₂L₂ under ambient conditions; the PCy₃ groups are mutually *trans* in both the isomers¹⁶¹. The five-coordinate dicarbonyls M(CO)₂L₂ (L=PPh₃; M/νCO=

Ru/1905, Os/1895) are obtained as yellow crystals by the deprotonation of [HM(CO)₂L₂]⁺ with methoxide. Dioxygen will substitute a PPh₃ molecule in M(CO)₂L₂ to produce M(CO)₂(O₂)L₂ (νRuO₂/νOsO₂=849/820). Since H₂, C₂H₄ and PhC≡CPh rapidly add on to the Ru dicarbonyl, it is suggested that the complex may dissociate in solution to Ru(CO)₂L₂ and L. It may be noted that Ru(CO)₂(C₂H₄)L₂ is the first ethylene complex of Ru to be reported¹⁶².

The five-coordinate tricarbonyl Ru(CO)₃L₂ (L/νCO=PPh₃/1900), which is an active homogeneous hydrogenation catalyst¹⁶³, is prepared by the NaBH₄ reduction of aq. RuCl₃ in presence of PPh₃ and aq. HCHO in boiling methoxyethanol¹⁶⁴. The Os analog is also known⁵. The oxidation of the tricarbonyls M(CO)₃L₂ with the diazonium salt, [PhN₂]⁺PF₆⁻ in dichloromethane/benzene affords five-coordinate cationic species [M(CO)₃(NNPh)L₂]⁺PF₆⁻ (with trigonal bipyramidal structure), which in presence of anions form MX(CO)₃(NNPh)L₂ (X=halogen, N₃, NCO). For the Os carbonyls νNN found near 1455 cm⁻¹ is the lowest value to be reported for a non-bridging aryl azo group¹⁶⁵.

A variety of six-coordinate carbonyl complexes of the formulae MX₂(CO)L₂ r MX₂(CO)₂L₂ (X=halogen, anionic ligand; L=tertiary phosphine, arsine) have been well established. The Ru carbonyls are conveniently prepared by passing CO through an alcoholic/methoxyethanol solution of aq. RuX₃ with the ligand; several of these (dicarbonyls) are isolated in isomeric forms^{6,166-170}. The *cis* dicarbonyl compounds (Conf. III) in solution (THF, CHCl₃, C₆H₆ or Me₂CO) on UV light irradiation isomerise to *all trans* forms (Conf. IV), which further convert into *all cis* forms (Conf. V) and subsequently to *cis* dicarbonyls (Conf. III) on heating. Likewise, the photochemical isomerisation

Scheme 12

Scheme 13

o° monocarbonyls $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{CO})(\text{PMe}_2\text{Ph})_2\text{L}'$ [$\text{L}' = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$, POMe_3 , $\text{P}(\text{OMe})_3\text{Ph}$] has also been investigated. Kinetics and mechanism of light and heat induced rearrangements have been discussed¹⁷¹. The dicarbonyls (all *cis* or *trans*; Conf. IV and V) react with HgR_2 ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Et, Ph}$) or SnMe_4 to give $\text{RuClR}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$, PMePh_2)¹⁷². On boiling a methoxy-ethanol solution of $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{CO})_2(\text{SP})_2$ ($\text{SP} = o\text{-CH}_2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{PPh}_2$) three new octahedral carbonyl complexes are obtained¹⁷³. Synthesis and structure elucidation of a variety of dicarbonyl complexes $\text{RuX}_2(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{halogen}$; $\text{L} = \text{Py, Pip}$; $\text{L}_2 = \text{dppe, bipy}$ etc.) have been made by Hieber and John^{174,175}. The azobenzene complex $[\text{Ru}(\text{azb})(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}]_2$ undergoes substitution/addition reactions with nucleophiles ($\text{Py, bipy, Pyz, PPh}_3, \text{dppe}$ etc.) or electrophiles ($\text{NaCp, TICp, Me}_4\text{NCl}$ etc.) to yield six-coordinate neutral and/or ionic complexes¹⁷⁶.

Isolation of six-coordinate complexes *cis*- $[\text{Os}(\text{CO})(\text{N}_3)(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{X}_2$ and $[\text{Os}(\text{CO})(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{halogen}$) has been claimed by Allen and Stevens¹⁷⁷. Chatt and coworkers¹⁷⁸ have synthesised monocarbonyls $\text{OsCl}_2(\text{CO})\text{L}_3$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}/1947$, $\text{PET}_3\text{Ph}/1941$; CO trans to L) by bubbling CO into a refluxing THF solution of OsCl_3L_3 in presence of amalgamated zinc;

the compounds isomerise ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}/1930$; CO trans to Cl) on refluxing in ethanol. Use of an excess amalgamated zinc in the above system (*mer*- OsCl_3L_3 in THF) yield yellow dicarbonyl complexes *trans*- $\text{OsCl}_2(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PET}_3, \text{PMePh}_2, \text{PETPh}_2, \text{PET}_2\text{Ph}, \text{PPR}_2\text{Ph}, \text{PBu}_2\text{Ph}, \text{AsMe}_2\text{Ph}$). The PET_3 complex of this series shows a 1:4:6:4:1 quintet due to P-CH_3 resonance typical of *trans* PET_3 groups, and has IR spectral bands at 1979 and 3125 cm^{-1} due to νCO and νCl (CO trans to Cl) groups respectively, indicating a *trans* octahedral geometry. The dicarbonyls ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO} = \text{PETPh}_2/1980$) also isomerise to white *cis* dicarbonyls ($\nu\text{CO} = 2037, 1971$) on refluxing in toluene. Phenyl isocyanide displaces one of the two CO groups of the *trans* dicarbonyl ($\text{L} = \text{PET}_3$) to form the yellow monocarbonyl *trans*- $\text{OsCl}_2(\text{CO})(\text{PhNC})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{OsCl}/\nu\text{CN} = 305/2160$; $\nu\text{CO} = 1940, 1950$), which undergoes oxidation with HNO_3 and HClO_4 to afford the green Os(III) cationic complex $[\text{OsCl}_2(\text{CO})(\text{PhNC})\text{L}_2]\text{ClO}_4$ ($\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{CN} = 2040/2195$). The Os(II) carbonyls $[\text{OsCl}(\text{CO})(\text{RNC})\text{L}_3]\text{ClO}_4$ ($\text{R} = \text{Me, Ph}$; $\text{L} = \text{PET}_3, \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$) are prepared by reduction of the corresponding $[\text{OsCl}_2(\text{RNC})\text{L}_3]\text{ClO}_4$ compounds by ethanol and CO ⁴¹. On refluxing a DMF solution of aq. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{OsCl}_6$ with L gives $[\text{OsCl}_2(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2]\text{Cl}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3$; $\nu\text{OsCl}/\nu\text{CO} = 334/1940$)¹⁷⁹.

Scheme 14

Action of sodium hydroxide on an ethanol solution of RuCl_2L_2 or a methoxyethanol solution of OsCl_2 ($\text{P-C})\text{L}_2$ [$\text{L}=\text{PMe}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7)$; $\text{P-C}=\text{PMe}_2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_6^-)$] yields six-coordinate metallated phosphine carbonyl complexes $\text{RuCl}(\text{P-C})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{CO}=1942\text{s}$) and $\text{Os}(\text{P-C})_2(\text{CO})\text{L}$ ($\nu\text{CO}=1922$ vs) respectively, whereas use of CO in place of sodium hydroxide in a suitable solvent affords octahedral complexes $\text{MCl}_2(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ [$\text{M}(\nu\text{CO})=\text{Ru}(1935$ vs, $1919\text{m})$, $\text{Os}(1923$ vs, 1911m ; $\text{CO trans to Cl})$] 180 .

can be easily displaced by anions and *p*-tNC respectively to give $\text{Rh}\{\text{ON}(\text{CF}_3)_2\}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{CO}=1960$), $\text{IrX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ [$\text{X}=(\text{CF}_3)_2\text{NO}$, SH , SCN , NCO , F , OH , CN etc.]] and [$\text{Ir}(\text{p-tNC})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$] $^+$ ($\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{CN}=2030/2180$) $^{186-188}$. The preparation of four-coordinate isocyanide carbonyl cation [$\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{p-tNC})_3$] $^+$ has also been reported 188 . Complexes of the type $\text{RhX}(\text{CO})(\text{p-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NC})_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, Br) have been isolated by Parish and Simms 189 , by reacting $[\text{RhX}(\text{CO})_2]_2$ with isonitrile at 0°C .

Scheme 15

(ii) Rhodium and Iridium

These metals form an extensive series of four-, five- and six-coordinate carbonyl complexes. The four- and five-coordinate complexes undergo facile oxidative addition and substitution reactions.

A variety of square-planar carbonyl compounds of Rh(I) and Ir(I) of the general formula *trans*- $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand; $\text{L}=\text{tertiary phosphine}$ or arsine) have been synthesised. Electrolysis of Vaska's complex $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) on anodically polarized mercury electrodes in dichloromethane and Bu_4NClO_4 leads to the formation of a mixture of species which further react with halide ions to yield $[\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]\text{HgX}_2$ [$\text{X}(\nu\text{CO}/\lambda_{\text{max}})=\text{Cl}(2035/290)$, $\text{Br}(2035/290,335)$, $\text{I}(2040/290,315,367)$] 181 . An $\text{S}_\text{N}2$ mechanism has been suggested for the oxidative addition of HgX_2 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}, \text{Br}$) to $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ in benzene. The crystal structure of the resultant complex $\text{IrClX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2\text{Hg}$ has been determined; Hg and X occupy axial positions in the octahedral geometry [the bond lengths, when $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ (Br), are $\text{Ir-Hg}=257$ (257.8), $\text{Ir-Cl}=245.3$ (258.6) and 240.1 (241), $\text{Ir-P}=238.7$ (241) and 237.8 (239), $\text{Ir-C}=180$ (180) and $\text{C-O}=114$ (111.5) pm] 181a . Brady *et al* 182 have recorded the electronic spectra of $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand; $\text{L}=\text{tertiary phosphine}$ or arsine) in benzene and related solutions at 25°C . As the absorption bands for the Ir compounds are sharper than their Rh analogs, the spectrochemical series for the ligands have been somewhat better defined in the case of Ir compounds. Garrou and Hartwell 182a have spectroscopically investigated the ligand (CO , X , L) exchange in $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, Br ; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, PEt_2Ph etc.). Peone and Vaska 188 have reported the substitution of chloride in *trans*- $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) by perchlorate on reacting the carbonyl with AgClO_4 . In the presence of polar solvents, solvent coordinated species $[\text{M}(\text{CO})(\text{S})\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\text{S}=\text{Me}_2\text{CO}$) are formed 184 . Substitution of the solvent molecule by L occurs to produce $[\text{M}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3]^+$ ($\text{L}=\text{PMePh}_2$, PEtPh_2 , PPh_3) 185 . The solvent molecule in the cation ($\text{S}/\text{L}=\text{MeCN}/\text{PPh}_3$; $\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{CN}=1975/2290$)

The perchlorate coordinated carbonyl *trans*- $\text{M}(\text{OClO}_3)(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$; $\text{M}/\nu\text{CO}=\text{Rh}/2000$, $\text{Ir}/1990$) undergoes facile substitution reactions with neutral molecules/olefins to give $[\text{M}(\text{CO})\text{QL}_2]^+$ [$\text{Q}=\text{C}_2\text{H}_4$, Py , Pip , EtNH_2 , Et_2NH , en, phosphines, PPh_3 ($\text{M}/\nu\text{CO}=\text{Rh}/2030$, $\text{Ir}/2020$), AsPh_3 , SbPh_3 , BiPh_3 etc.]] 190 , and with anions yields $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{BH}_4$, BH_3CN ; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, PCy_3) 191 . Action of a THF solution of sodium cyclopentadienide on $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) or RhClL_2 and CO in benzene leads to the formation of $\text{MCp}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$. The Ir complex forms adducts with Lewis acids, ZnBr_2 , HgCl_2 , TlCl_3 etc. 193 . The crystal structure determination suggests a planar triangular arrangement of the ligands in $\text{IrCp}(\text{CO})\text{L}$ ($\nu\text{CO}=1944$) with $\text{Ir-Cp}(\text{av.})=227.2$, $\text{Ir-CO}=180$ and $\text{C-O}=117.6$ pm. The Ir-P bond length of 223.7 pm is found to be the shortest observed for Ir complexes 194 . Oxidation of $\text{MCp}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ with $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{CN}$ in presence of NaBPh_4 yields $[\text{MCp}(\text{CO})(\text{CH}_2\text{CN})\text{L}]\text{BPh}_4$ 195 . Li(carb) reacts with $\text{MCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ in benzene to form *trans*- $\text{M}(\sigma\text{-carb})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PP}_3$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O}_2\text{h}_8$, PMePh_2 ; carb = 2-R-1, 2-B $_{10}$ -C $_2$ H $_{10}$, 7-R-1, 7-B $_{10}$ -C $_2$ H $_{10}$; R=H, Me; R'=R, Ph) which further undergoes irreversible oxidative addition of H_2 yielding three different isomers 196,197 . Similarly, $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) reacts with $\text{Li}(\text{Mes})(\text{Mes}=\text{C}\equiv\text{CPh}$, 2,4,6-C $_6$ H $_2$ Me $_3$) to give $\text{Ir}(\text{Mes})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$; the complex ($\text{Mes}=2,4,6\text{-C}_6\text{H}_2\text{Me}_3$) forms as an easily separable 10:1 mixture of *cis* (red, $\nu\text{CO}=1954\text{vs}$) and *trans* (yellow, $\nu\text{CO}=1949\text{vs}$) isomers 198 .

Metathetical displacement of chloride from $\text{MCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) by reaction with $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{STI}$, $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{-MgBr}$ or $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{Li}/\text{AgLiR}$ ($\text{R}=\text{Ph}$, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl etc.) yields *trans*- $\text{MR}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ 199,200 . The crystal structure determination on the Ir carbonyl ($\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{F}_5$) suggests a slightly distorted planar structure with bond distances, $\text{Ir-P}=232.6$, 230.5 , $\text{Ir-C}_6\text{F}_5=209$, $\text{Ir-CO}=189.1$ and $\text{C-O}=113.7$ pm 199 . Both the Rh and Ir carbonyls ($\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{F}_5$) add on oxidatively halogens, mercuric halides, SO_2 , $\text{C}_6\text{F}_5\text{SH}$ etc. 201 . In contrast, $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})(\text{o-tolyl})_2$ ($\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{IrCO}=1948/603$; $\nu\text{IrCl}/\lambda_{\text{max.}}=315/329, 376$) is unreactive towards H_2 , O_2 , SO_2 and cyano-olefins, and

the lack of reactivity has been attributed to the location of *o*-CH₃ groups near the apical positions as shown by X-ray analysis (Ir-P=233.8, Ir-Cl=243, Ir-CO=167 and C-O=118 pm)²⁰². For comparison, Ir-CO and Ir-C(*σ*) bond lengths in several carbonyls have been collected²⁰⁰. Crystal structure of the dicarbonyl IrCl(CO)₂Py, suggests a square-planar configuration with Ir-CO(av.)=181.3 pm²⁰³; the carbonyl is obtained by the displacement of a chloride with Py in [IrCl₂(CO)₂]⁻ anion²⁰⁴. Treatment of IrX(CO)L₂ (X/L=halogen, N₃/PPh₃, Cl/PMe₂Ph, PEt₂Ph, PEtPh₂, PBuⁿPh₂) with PnCON₃ in chloroform at 0°C, leads to the formation of dinitrogen complexes IrX(N₂)₂L₂²⁰⁵; a ν_{NN} band around 2100 cm⁻¹ (2331 for N₂ gas) is found in the IR spectra of these complexes¹⁷⁸.

Reddy and coworkers²⁰⁶⁻²⁰⁸ have isolated novel four-coordinate cationic complexes of the composition *cis*-[Rh(CO)₂(N-N)]ClO₄ [N-N(ν_{CO})=bipy(2108, 2050), phen(2103, 2042)] by the addition of N-N to an alcoholic carbonylated solution of rhodium perchlorate. If *o*-tolyl₃P is used in place of N-N in the above system, *trans*-[Rh(CO)₂(*o*-tolyl₃P)₂]ClO₄ (ν_{CO}=2040) will be formed. The *cis* dicarbonyls have also been synthesised by Cocevar, Mestroni and Camus⁹⁵, starting from [Rh(COD)(N-N)]⁺. Further, these workers²⁰⁹ have suggested that the dicarbonyls prepared by Reddy and coworkers^{206,207} are to be formulated as [Rh(CO)₂(N-N)]⁺. This claim has, however, been found now to be not correct²¹⁰. Similarly, the claim on the formation of [Ir(CO)₂(N-N)]⁺ (ν_{CO}=2089, 2024) from [Ir(COD)(N-N)]⁺ and CO²¹¹, or [IrCl(CO)₂]_x and

bipy²⁰⁴ may have to be again reconfirmed. However, it has been stated that this tricarbonyl (in MeCN) loses a molecule of CO on passage of C₂H₄ followed by argon, to form the dicarbonyl cation [Ir(CO)₂(N-N)]⁺; this reacts reversibly with nucleophilic olefins—butene, COD etc., and undergoes oxidative addition reactions with HgCl₂, HgBr₂, HCl, H₂ and I₂²¹¹. Gillard *et al*²¹² have prepared two forms—yellow(ν_{CO}=2104, 2040) and green (ν_{CO}=2114, 2060)—of the phen derivative [Rh(CO)₂phen][ClO₄]. The dicarbonyls containing monodentate ligands, [Rh(CO)₂Q₂]⁺ (Q=Py, 2-MePy, 4-MePy, 2-vinylPy) are formed on reacting the cations [Rh(COD)Q₂]⁺ with CO²¹³. Treatment of [Rh(CO)₂(N-N)]⁺ (in MeCN or Me₂CO under nitrogen) with LiX (X=Cl, Br, I) produces four-coordinate neutral complexes RhX(CO)(N-N)²⁰⁹.

[RhCl(CO)₂]₂ undergoes chloride bridge splitting in benzene on treatment with PPh₃ (L) and amines (Q) respectively to give *trans*-RhCl(CO)₂L (ν_{CO}=1980vs) and *cis*-RhCl(CO)₂Q (Q=Py, *p*-td, An, Pic, MeNH₂, PhNH₂)^{214,215}. The former product has been reformulated as *trans*-[RhCl(CO)L]₂²¹⁶; this reacts with neutral molecules to yield mixed carbonyls RhCl(CO)L' (L'=AsPh₃, Py, *p*-tolylNH₂, Me₂S)²¹⁵. Substitution of L in Rh(NO)L₂ by CO affords Rh(CO)(NO)L₂²¹⁷. The Ir analog has also been synthesised; crystal structure of the complex shows a distorted tetrahedral geometry with Ir-C=187.3 and C-O=114.4 pm²¹⁸.

Empsall, Hyde and Shaw⁶⁵ have obtained some unusual complexes of the type Ir(CO)₂PBu₂(C₆H₄O) L

Scheme 16

[L=PBu₃(C₆H₄OX-2); X=H, D, Me] by bubbling CO into a methoxyethanol solution of Na₂IrCl₆ in presence of L. Crystal structure determination of the complexes of the type MCl(CO){PBu₃(CH₂)₂OBu₃P} suggests a *trans* mononuclear configuration for the Ir complex [Ir-Cl=240.5, Ir-P(av.)=236.2 and Ir-CO=191.2 pm] and a dinuclear configuration for the Rh complex [Rh-P(av.)=236.5 pm]²¹⁹. Polyphosphines react with MCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂ in benzene to give cationic complexes [M(CO)(triphos/tetraphos)]Cl²²⁰. Passage of CO through a dichloromethane-acetone solution of RhCl(ttp) in presence of NaPF₆ produces [Rh(CO)₂(ttp)]PF₆ (νCO=1940, 2040vs) which loses a molecule of CO, on sweeping with nitrogen, to give [Rh(CO)(ttp)]PF₆ (νCO=2025vs). Addition of CO to RhCl(ttp) also occurs to yield RhCl(CO)(ttp) (νCO=1956)⁹¹. Japanese workers²²¹ have kinetically investigated the adduct formation of a series of complexes RhX(CO)L₂ (X=halogen; L=PPh₃, PMePh₂, *p*-tolyl₃P, AsPh₃) and IrCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂ with TCNE in solvents—Me₂CO, THF and PhCN. The νCO value shifts to a higher region in these products. The crystal structure analysis suggests an octahedral configuration for the complex IrCl(CO)(AsPh₃)₂ (TCNE) with CO and Cl groups occupying the axial positions [Ir-As(av.)=248, Ir-Cl=235.4, Ir-C(av.)=210.7, Ir-CO=182.6 and C-O=120 pm]²²². Bidentate phosphines react with IrCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂ in benzene to form [Ir(CO)(P-P)₂]Cl (P-P=dpp, dae etc.; νCO~1930)^{222a}.

Displacement of the solvent molecule in [M(CO)(S)L₂]⁺ (L=tertiary phosphine) by CO occurs to yield five-coordinate tricarbonyl [M(CO)₃L₂]⁺ cations^{201,202}. The tricarbonyls of Ir are also obtained by bubbling CO into an acetone solution of IrCl(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃, PMePh₂, PEt₂Ph, PET₃, PCy₃, PPr₃, AsPh₃) in presence of NaBPh₄²²³. Refluxing a chloroform solution of these tricarbonyls (L=PCy₃, PPr₃) under nitrogen results in the loss of a molecule of CO to afford [Ir(CO)₂L₂]⁺. The cations [M(CO)L₃]⁺ and [M(CO)₃L₂]⁺ respectively undergo addition of CO or substitution of CO by L to produce [M(CO)₂L₃]⁺ species. The dicarbonyl cations of Rh are also prepared by passing CO into an alcoholic solution of rhodium perchlorate in presence of L (L=PPh₃, *p*-tolyl₃P, AsPh₃, AsMePh₂, AsEtPh₂, AsPrPh₂, SbPh₃). Trigonal bipyramidal configuration has been suggested for these cations^{200,201}. Deeming and Shaw²²⁴ have synthesised a series of five-coordinate cationic carbonyls [Ir(CO)₂(L_{3-x})]⁺ (x=1-3; L=PMe₂Ph, AsMe₂Ph) starting from IrCl(CO)L₂. Several of these four and five-coordinate cations undergo oxidative addition (of HX, H₂, Cl₂, MeX, HgX₂ etc.) and substitution reactions. A variety of five-coordinate thio-carbonyl cations [Ir(CO)₂(CS)(L₂)]⁺ (L=PPh₃, PCy₃) and [Ir(CO)(CS)(PMePh₂)₂]⁺ have been synthesised starting from *trans*-IrCl(CS)L₂ and CO, by Mays and Stefanini²²⁵. The crystal structure determination of [Ir(CO)₂(CS)(PPh₃)₂]PF₆ (νCS/νCO=1319s/2005,2047) suggests a trigonal bipyramidal geometry for the cation;

Scheme 17

the bond lengths (of two forms) are Ir-P=236.7 & 237.2, Ir-CS=186.3 & 187.1, Ir-CO=192.6 & 194.9, and C-O=118.2 & 117.9 pm^{22,25}.

A methanolic suspension of IrCl(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃) reacts with CS₂ in presence of L and NaBPh₄ to give an unusual complex [Ir(S₂CPPH₃)(CO)L₂]BPh₄. ν CO=1980) as violet crystals; the crystal structure indicates a distorted trigonal bipyramidal configuration for the cation with CO and one S atom located at the axial positions (Ir-P=232.4, 233.4; Ir-S=231.2, 237.9; Ir-CO=190 and C-O=111 pm)^{22,27}. Action of CF₃CN on Ir(π -1/2-MeC₃H₄)(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃) in benzene gives CCF₃N=CCF₃(CO)L₂ (ν CO=1990) and Ir(NH=CCF₃N=CCF₃NH)(CO)L₂ (ν CO=1973) respectively; the X-ray crystal structure of the latter complex suggests a square-planar coordination for the central Ir atom (Ir-P=227.1, Ir-N=202.3, 202.8 and Ir-CO=183.1 pm)^{22,28}. Flynn and Vaska^{22,29} have described the reversible addition of CO₂ (IR bands, 2349 & 667) to M(OH)(CO)L₂ (L/ ν CO=PPh₃/1950) in the solid state to form M(OH)(CO)₂(CO)L₂ (ν CO/ ν CO₂=1966vs/1602, 1351s, 821m). However, in ethanol medium, thermally stable bicarbonate compounds M(OCO₂H)(CO)L₂ (bicarbonate acts as a monodentate ligand) are formed. Similarly, the hydroxy carbonyls react with COS to give M(OCOSH)(CO)L₂. Addition of carbon diselenide to IrCl(CO)L₂ affords IrCl(CSe₂)(CO)L₂ (ν CO=2025)^{1,22}.

The four- and five-coordinate carbonyl complexes undergo oxidative addition reactions with molecules—possessing both polar and non-polar bonds—such as hydrogen halides, alkyl halides, acyl halides, pseudo-halogens protonic acids, olefins, acetylenes, metal halides, non-metal hydrides, halogens, dihydrogen and dioxygen, to give, normally, octahedral complexes^{23,30}. Since the ease of oxidative addition increases upon descending a triad, Rh complexes are less reactive towards oxidative addition than those of Ir. Vaska^{23,31} has described the thermodynamic data, and has compared the values for the reversible addition of some small molecules to isostructural d⁸ complexes of Rh and Ir. IrCl(CO)L₂ + XY \rightleftharpoons (XY)IrCl(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃; XY=HX, X₂, H₂, O₂, SO₂, CO, C₂H₄, TCNE etc.).

It has been found that the stability and heats of formation of metal complex adducts with acid molecules (H₂, O₂, SO₂) are (or appear to be): third row > second row metal (Ir > Rh). Wickman and Silverthorn^{23,32} have made Mössbauer spectral studies on several of these adducts. Halpern^{23,33} has suggested the following mechanism for the oxidative addition of dihydrogen, halogens and hydrohalic acids to Ir(I) carbonyl complexes (Scheme 18). Depending on the conditions—nature of the solvents and reactants—(both *cis* and/or *trans* modes of addition have been reported. Carbonyl stretching band for the M(III) complexes will be at a higher region when compared to the parent M(I) carbonyls.

Rh(I) carbonyls are comparatively hard towards dioxygen adduct formation than the Ir analogs. So, a variety of dioxygen adducts of Ir, IrX(CO)(O₂)L₂, Ir(Ar)(CO)(O₂)L₂, Ir(SR)(CO)(O₂)L₂ and [Ir(CO)(O₂)L₃]⁺ (X=halogen, anionic ligand; Ar=aryl group; R=alkyl or aryl group; L=tertiary phosphine or arsine) have been synthesised^{7,6,18,8,18,8,19,9,23,4-24,0}; several of these adducts are reversible. In some cases the coordinated ligand itself gets oxidised as found in the reaction of IrClX(CO)(NO)L₂ (X=halogen, NCS, NCO, N₃; L=PPh₃) with O₂, to give IrClX(CO)(NO₃)L₂; kinetic studies on these reactions have been attempted^{24,1}. The SO₂ adducts, (IrX(CO)(SO₂))L₂ react with dioxygen to form sulphate adducts IrX(CO)(SO₄)L₂ (X/L=SC₆F₅/PPh₃, Cl/AsPh₃)^{20,1,28,9}. Similarly, RhCl(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃) in presence of CO and O₂ gets converted to RhCl(CO)₂(Ph₃PO)₂. Recently, it has been found that the photochemical (366 nm) oxidation of *trans*-RhCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂ (ν CO=1974) in dichloromethane saturated with air affords an oligomeric complex [RhCl(O₂)(Ph₃PO)_{0.67}]_n, Ph₃PO and CO₂ (CO₂ has been detected by an IR band at 2377 cm⁻¹)^{24,1,0}. However, it is surmised that RhCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂ forms a reversible 1:1 adduct with O₂ and this probably enhances the auto-oxidation of an organic substrate^{23,6}. Although the isologous dinitrogen adducts have not been isolated, formation of the yellow complex Rh₂Cl₄(N₂)(CO)₂L₂.2NH₄C (L=PPh₃), from Rh(acac)(CO)L and excess HN₃ in

Scheme 18

dichloromethane-pentane at -60°C , has been claimed by Russian workers²⁴².

νCO of dioxygen adducts shifts to a higher region when compared to the parent compounds. In addition, a νOO band appears in the $800\text{--}900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region of the infrared, and this shifts to a lower region on isotopic substitution²⁴³. It has been shown by X-ray studies that the O-O bond length of the coordinated dioxygen ($\sim 130\text{ pm}$) will be longer than 121 pm observed in free O_2 yet less than 149 pm in peroxide (O_2^{2-}), but will be very near to that of 133 pm found in superoxide (O_2^-)²³⁴⁻²³⁶. For dioxygen complexes of the type $\text{MX}(\text{CO})(\text{O}_2)\text{L}_2$, the structure has been suggested to be as intermediary between five- ($d\text{ s }p^3$) and six-coordinate ($d^2\text{ s }p^3$)²³⁷. The most important property of some of the dioxygen containing complexes is their ability to catalyse (isomerisation²⁴⁴ and) the oxygenation of organic substrates usually under mild conditions. Thus, oxidation of cyclohexene to cyclohexenone has been reported in the presence of $\text{MX}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$)²⁴⁵.

Oxidative addition of polar molecules (XY) to the perchlorate coordinated carbonyl $\text{M}(\text{CO})(\text{OCIO}_4)\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3, \text{PCy}_3$) occurs to produce $\text{MXY}(\text{CO})(\text{OCIO}_4)\text{L}_2$ ($\text{XY}=\text{H}_2, \text{HCl}, \text{Cl}_2$, organic halides carboxylic acids etc.); νCO values of several resultant products have been correlated with pK_a values of the reactant carboxylic acids (RCOOH) and the conjugate acids of the amines (R_3NH^+)¹⁹⁰. Blake, Shields and Wyman²⁴⁶ have reported the oxidative addition of carboxylic anhydrides, RCO_2COR ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{CF}_3$

complexes; while the addition of the latter is *cis*, the former is *trans*. The ligand, dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate reacts with tricarbonyl anionic, $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_3\text{L}_2]^+$ to give hexa-coordinate adducts of the composition $[\text{Ir}(\text{MeO}_2\text{CC}\equiv\text{CCO}_2\text{Me})(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2]^+$ [$\nu\text{CO}_2\text{Me}/\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{C}\sim 1700/1800$; $\text{L}(\nu\text{CO})=\text{PPh}_3$ (2089, 2091), PMePh_2 (2038, 2086), PEt_3 (2044, 2088), PCy_3 (2018, 2068).]²²³. The carbonyls $\text{RhX}(\text{CO})(\text{RNC})_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$; $\text{R}=\textit{p}\text{-MeOC}_6\text{H}_4$) add on halogens to form $\text{RhClBr}_2(\text{CO})(\text{RNC})_2$ and $\text{RhBr}_2(\text{CO})(\text{RNC})_2$ ¹⁸⁹. Similarly, $\text{RhX}(\text{CO})(\text{N-N})$ ($\text{N-N}=\text{bipy, phen}$) complexes form adducts with acetylene, AcN , FMN , TCNE and MeI^{200} . Bromine oxidises $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{QL}_2]^+$ ($\text{Q}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) to $\text{IrBr}_2(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{Br})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ^{244a}. Likewise, the Py complex ($\text{Q}=\text{Py}$) with $\text{RC}\equiv\text{CR}$ ($\text{R}=\text{CF}_3, \text{CO}_2\text{CH}_3$) affords $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{Py}(\text{RC}=\text{CR})\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{C}=\text{C}\sim 2000/1780$)²⁴⁴. The $\text{MX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ complexes undergo oxidative addition of $\text{PhC}(\text{Cl})=\text{NMe}$ and $1,2\text{-BrB}_5\text{H}_8$ respectively to yield octahedral complexes $\text{RhCl}_2(\text{CO})(\text{PhCNHMe})\text{L}$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO}=\text{PMePh}_2/\sim 2100$)²⁴⁷ and $2\text{-}[\text{IrBr}_2(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]\text{B}_5\text{H}_8$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO}=\text{PMe}_3/2024\text{ s}$; $\nu\text{BH}/\delta\text{BH}=2573\text{ m, }2554\text{ m}/945\text{ s}$; crystal structure investigation suggests a regular octahedral geometry for the latter complex [$\text{Ir-P}(\text{av.})=236.15$, $\text{Ir-Br}(\text{av.})=257.7$ and $\text{Ir-CO}=195\text{ pm}$)²⁴⁸. Ethynyl dicarbododecarborane with $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) forms a 2:1 adduct, $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2(\text{B}_{10}\text{C}_4\text{H}_{12})_2$ ($\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{C}\equiv\text{C}=2080/2140$; $\nu\text{BH}=2598$)²⁴⁹.

C_2F_5) and $\text{CF}_3\text{CO}_2\text{COCF}_3$ to $\text{IrX}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{Cl, Br}$; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2$) to get octahedral Ir(III) carbonyl

Oxidation of $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ with MeY results in the formation of $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2(\text{Me})(\text{Y})(\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$; $\text{Y}=\text{SO}_2\text{F, SO}_2\text{CF}_3$) which further undergoes dissociation in nitromethane to $[\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2\text{Me}]^+$ and SO_3F^- species²⁵⁰. Complexes of the type $\text{IrCl}(\text{ON}(\text{CF}_3)_2)_2(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO}=\text{PPh}_3/2052$, $\text{AsPh}_3/2058$, $\text{PMePh}_2/2058$) have

$\text{X}=\text{halogen, anionic ligand}$; $\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, tertiary phosphine; $\text{P-P}=\text{dpp, dae, vaa}$ etc.

Scheme 19

Pt(CO)(PPh₃)₃ suggests that it has approximately tetrahedral geometry [Pt-P=33.4 (P *trans* to P), 235.2 (P *trans* to CO) and Pt-CO=186 pm]^{269,260}. The stability of the dicarbonyls Pt(CO)₂(PRPh₂)₂, it has been suggested, depends on steric requirements of the group R of the ligand, PRPh₂²⁵⁸.

Four-coordinate carbonyl complexes of Pt(II) of the type PtX₂(CO)L have been made by cleavage of the halogen bridges of the dimer [PtX₂L]₂ (X=halogen; L=Py, *p*-tolyl NH₂, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-tolyl₃P, PMe₃, PEt₃, PBu₃, PPh₃, P-γ₃) with CO^{13,261}, or of the carbonyl dimer [PtX₂(CO)]₂ by AsMePh₂^{13,15}. Vrieze and coworkers²⁶² have investigated the bonding properties in complexes PtX₂(CO)L (X=Cl, Br; L=nitrogen donor ligand) using electronic, IR, Raman, and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral methods. The molecular structure of *cis*-PtCl₂(CO)(PPh₃) has been determined [Pt-Cl=227.7 (Cl *trans* to CO), 234.2 (Cl *trans* to P); Pt-P=227.9 pm]²⁶³. A number of cationic carbonyl complexes *trans*-[PtX(CO)L₂]⁺ (X=halogen, anionic ligand; L=tertiary phosphine or arsine) have been synthesised by passing CO into an acetone suspension of PtX₂L₂ in presence of sodium perchlorate^{124,264}, or by bridge splitting of [PtXL₂]₂[BF₄]₂ with CO^{265,266}. These compounds show the diagnostic νCO band around 2100 cm⁻¹ in the infrared. *trans*-PtCl(CO)L₂⁺ (L=PEt₃) reacts with water and alcohols (MeOH, EtOH) or carboxylic acid esters to give HPtCl₂ and PtCl(-COOR)L₂ respectively²⁶⁵. X-ray crystal structures of the cations *trans*-[PtCl(CO)L₂]⁺ (Pt-Cl/Pt-P=230/234.5; Pt-CO/C-O=178/114 pm)²⁶⁷ and *trans*-[Pt(*p*-ClC₆H₄)(CO)L₂]⁺ (Pt-P/Pt-CO=230/197; C-O=106 pm)²⁶⁸ have been determined. Recently, synthesis of a cationic dinuclear carbonyl [Pt₂(CO)₂ (C≡CC₆H₄C≡C)L₄] [ClO₄]₂ has been reported²⁶⁹.

Kingston and Scollary²⁷⁰ have reported the anionic carbonyls of the types [MCl(CO)(SnCl₃)₂]⁻ (M/νCO=Pd/2054, Pt/2038 sh, 2058) and [PtCl(CO)(SnCl₃)₂(EtOH)]⁻. The Pt carbonyl anions react with nucleophiles to yield four- and five-coordinate neutral complexes Pt(CO)(SnCl₃)₂Py (νCO=2041), Pt(CO)(SnCl₃)₂phen (νCO=2046) and Pt(CO)(SnCl₃)₂(PPh₃)₂ (νCO=2050).

Treatment of Pt(Bu^tNC)₂L₂ (L/νCN=PPh₃/2030) with CO leads to the formation of four-coordinate isocyanide carbonyl Pt(CO)(Bu^tNC)L₂ (νCO/νCN=1910/2110) as a pale yellow solid. The increase in νCN (80 cm⁻¹) suggests that CO is a much more effective π-acceptor ligand than the isoelectronic isocyanide²⁷¹. Treichel and Knebel²⁷² have claimed the formation of an unstable intermediate carbonyl dication [Pt(CO)(MeNC)L₂]²⁺ in the reaction of [Pt(MeNC)(MeNHCO)L₂]⁺ with HBF₄ in aq. MeCN.

c) Hydrido carbonyls

Hydrido carbonyl complexes of all the platinum metals except those of Pd have been made. Normally, they contain one or more tertiary phosphine or arsine ligand(s). Several hydrido carbonyls in which hydride

and CO molecules are the only ligands present are also known for a long time. Such compounds, however, are not very stable. The stability of these can be increased by substitution of one or more CO group(s) by tertiary phosphine or arsine ligands. Almost all hydrido carbonyl complexes obey the 18e rule barring the four-coordinate Rh(I), Ir(I) and Pt(II) complexes, which conform to the 16e rule.

(i) Ruthenium and Osmium

A variety of octahedral hydrido carbonyl complexes of these metals have been synthesised. These complexes usually have one hydride ligand and one CO molecule in addition to the other ligands attached to the metal. However, there are also several compounds having more than one hydride ion and CO group.

The four-coordinate hydrido carbonyl complex HRu(CO)C_P(PPh₃)₃ (τ_H=24.93) has been obtained by the displacement of a CO molecule in HRu(CO)₂C_P with PPh₃²⁷³. Moers, Ten Hoedt and Langhout^{101,274,275} have synthesised five-coordinate complexes of the composition HMCl(CO)(PCy₃)₃ (νRuH/νCO=2030/1905; νOsH/νCO=2012/1887) by heating a methoxyethanol solution of RuCl₃ or K₂OsCl₆ with PCy₃. Treatment of the dihydrido carbonyl nitrosyl cation [H₂Os(CO)(NO)L₂]⁺ (L=PPh₃, PCy₃) with THF-EtOH or an excess of PCy₃ produces HOs(CO)(NO)L₂^{269,276}. Action of the diazonium salt [PhN₂]⁺PF₆⁻ on H₂M(CO)L₂ (L=PPh₃) yields the cationic complex [HM(CO)(HNNPh)L₂]⁺PF₆⁻ which undergoes deprotonation (of the coordinated group) with sodium hydroxide to form the neutral complex HM(CO)(NNPh)L₂ (νRuH/νCO=2012/1928; τ_H/J_{PH}=18.79t/21; νOsH/νCO=2010/1911; τ_H/J_{PH}=19.51t/21)¹⁶⁵. The crystal structure of the Os complex suggests a trigonal bipyramidal geometry [Os-P(av.)=283.7, Os-N=186.7 and Os-CO=187.8 pm; H atom is not located] with P atoms occupying the axial positions²⁷⁷. The complex is also obtained by the partial decarbonylation (using UV light) of HOs(CO)₂(NNPh)L₂¹⁶⁵.

The hydrido carbonyl HOsX(CO)L₂ (L=PCy₃) adds on dioxygen in benzene to form HOsX(CO)(O₂)L₂ (νCO/νOO=1950/820; X/τ_H=Cl/13.0t, Br/13.2t). Likewise, a variety of adducts of stoichiometry HMCl(CO)YL₂ (Y=SO₂, Py, C₂H₄, CO) have been isolated starting from HMCl(CO)L₂²⁷⁸. Insertion of CS₂ into the M-H bond of the five-coordinate hydrido carbonyl occurs to yield M(CO)(HCS₂)Cl₂ (M/νCO=Ru/1933, Os/1905), and the Os complex has been isolated in two forms (α and β)^{274,278}.

The six-coordinate hydrido carbonyls of the type HMX(CO)L₆ (X=halogen; L=tertiary phosphine or arsine) have been synthesised by several methods. For example, HMCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃ (νOsH/νCO=2097/1912; τ_H/J_{PH}=16.27dt/24.5, 87_t) complexes are obtained by boiling a methoxyethanol solution of RuCl₃ or Os salt and PPh₃ in presence of HCHO^{279,280} (or DMF¹⁷⁹). Both the hydrido carbonyls serve as homogeneous catalysts for olefin isomerization²⁸¹. In the octahedral complex HRuCl(CO)L₅ (L/νRuH=PPPh₃/1869;

$\tau_H/J_{PH}=17.5dt/25\sigma, 109\epsilon$), Douglas and Shaw²⁸² find that the ligand *trans* to H can be displaced by the more strongly bonding ligand PMe_2Ph to give $HRuCl(CO)L_2$ (PMe_2Ph)($\nu RuH=1874$; $\tau_H/J_{PH}=16.8 dt/25\sigma, 115\epsilon$). In the same way, Christian and Roper¹⁶⁰ have described the substitution of one of the PPh_3 molecules in $HRuCl(CO)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3$) by *p*-tNC to form $HRuCl(CO)L_2(p-tNC)(\nu CN/\nu CO=2140/1922, 1935$; $\tau_H/J_{PH}=15.5t/19$). The isocyanide complex further reacts with $AgClO_4$ to yield $HRu(OCIO_3)(CO)L_2(p-tNC)(\nu CN/\nu CO=2184/1947$; $\tau_H/J_{PH}=15.4t/18$) from which the coordinated perchlorate easily gets displaced on treatment with nucleophiles ($Q=CO, PPh_3$) to give $[HRu(CO)Q(p-tNC)L_2]ClO_4$ complexes. The dicarbonyl $[HRu(CO)_2(p-tNC)L_2]ClO_4$ has been isolated in two isomeric—*cis* and *trans* forms.

$HMCl(CO)L_3$ occurs, on treatment with $AgClO_4$ in acetonitrile, to give $[HM(CO)(MeCN)_2L_2]^+$ species²⁸³. The dicarbonyl $HOsCl(CO)_2L_2$ ($\nu OsH/\nu CO=1920/1975, 2035vs$) has been obtained by the displacement of L in $HOsCl(CO)L_2$ with CO ²⁸⁴. Deprotonation of $HMCl(CO)L_3$ with diazonium tetrafluoroborates yields $MCl(CO)(F_2B)(NH=NR)L_2$ ($R=p-MeC_6H_4, p-OMe-C_6H_4, p-ClC_6H_4$) complexes which further react with CO to produce dicarbonyl complexes $[MCl(CO)_2(NH=NR)L_2]BF_4$ ²⁸⁵. A hydrido tricarbonyl $HOsCl(CO)_3L$ ($\nu OsH/\nu CO=2100/1950, 2040$) has been prepared by refluxing a DMF solution of $OsCl_3$ and PPh_3 in the mole ratio 1 : 2¹⁷⁹. Protonation of the tricarbonyl $M(CO)_3L_2$ with non-coordinating acids ($HClO_4, HBF_4, HPF_6$)^{284, 286} affords the octahedral cation $[HM(CO)_3L_2]^+$, whereas with formic acid it forms

L = PPh_3 , tertiary phosphine; Q = CO, PPh_3 ; Y = SO_2 , Py, C_2H_4 , CO
 tri = 1,3-diaryl triazenido ligand; R = *p*- MeC_6H_4 , *p*- $OMeC_6H_4$, *p*- ClC_6H_4

Scheme 21

Laing, Robinson and Uttley³² have reported the synthesis of hydrido carbonyls of the formula $HM(CO)(tri)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3$; tri = 1,3-diaryl triazenido ligand; diaryl = di-*p*-tolyl; $M/\nu CO=Ru/1927$; $\tau_H/J_{PH}=22.37t/20.5$; $\nu OsH/\nu CO=2004/1903$; $\tau_H/J_{PH}=22.85t/18.5$). X-ray studies on the complex, *trans*- $HRu(p-MeC_6H_4-N_3C_6H_4Me-p)(CO)(PPh_3)_2$ indicate an octahedral coordination about Ru atom ($Ru-H=180$; $Ru-P=234.3, 235.4$; $Ru-N=214.9, 217.9$; $Ru-CO=185.6$ and $C-O=116.1 pm$)²⁸². Cleavage of the chloride in

a formate complex $M(CO)_2(HCO_2)L_2$. Displacement of the acetate group in $HRu(MeCO_2)L_2$ by CO in presence of a non-coordinating acid produces $[HRu(CO)_2(H_2O)L_2]^+$ species³³.

Bell, Chatt and Leigh⁴⁸ have synthesised octahedral dihydrido carbonyls $H_2Os(CO)L_2$ ($L=PMePh_2, PEtPh_2, PMe_2Ph, PEt_2Ph, AsEt_2Ph$) by treating H_4OsL_8 with CO. The Ru analogs ($L=PPh_3, PMePh_2$) have also

been reported^{289,290}. The PPh_3 complex undergoes deprotonation in presence of HCl to form $Ru_2Cl_4(CO)_2L_3$ ²⁸⁹. One of the CO groups in $H_2Os(CO)_4$ is substituted by a tertiary phosphine to get an octahedral dihydrido tricarbonyl $H_2Os(CO)_3L$ [τ_H/J_{PH}]= PPh_3 (18.0d/24), PBu_3 (18.97d/25)]²⁹⁰. Further displacement of a molecule of CO in $H_2Os(CO)_3L$ by L or oxidative addition of H_2 to $M(CO)_3L_2$ yields $H_2M(CO)_2L_2$ [$M(L)=Ru(PEt_3, PPh_3), Os(PBu_3, PPh_3)$]²⁹¹. The Os dihydrido dicarbonyl ($L=PPh_3$) reacts with fluorocarboxylic acids ($RCOOH$, $R=CF_3, C_2F_5, C_6F_5$) to afford $HO_3C(CO)_2(O_2CR)L_2$ ($R=CF_3; \nu_{OsH/\nu_{CO}}=2100w/1958, 2070; \tau_H/J_{PH}=27.8t/11.5$)⁴⁷. Oxidative addition of H_2 to the cation formed *in situ* from $OsCl(CO)(NO)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3, PCy_3$) and $AgPF_6$ in acetone, results in the formation of a dihydrido carbonyl nitrosyl [$H_2Os(C)(NO)L_2$]⁺ ($\nu_{OsH/\nu_{CO}}=2022-2120; \nu_{NO}=1772-1809; \tau_H=14.5-17.5t$)²⁷⁶.

(ii) Rhodium and Iridium

These metals form a large number of hydrido carbonyl complexes, the majority of them being octahedral. Many of these are obtained by oxidative addition reactions rather than substitution. Almost all these complexes obey the 18e rule except a few four-coordinate hydrido carbonyls which conform to the 16e rule.

Barefield *et al*²⁹² have reported the formation of the four-coordinate complex $HfR(CO)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3$) starting from $H_2I \cdot L_2$. Oliver and Graham²⁹³ have isolated the four-coordinate cyclopentadienyl hydrido carbonyl $HRh(CO)Cp(Ph_3Si)$ ($\nu_{CO}=2024; \tau_H/J_{PH}=21.1 d/31.8$). Protonation of $Ir(CO)CpL$ in presence of $NOPF_6$ affords $[HfR(CO)CpL]^+$ species^{192,294}. The five-coordinate complexes $HM(CO)L_3$ ($\nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}=2030/1915; \tau_H/J_{PH}=19.7/14; J_{RhH}<1; \nu_{IrH/\nu_{CO}}=2120/1915; \tau_H/J_{PH}=20.3 q/21.3$) have been conveniently prepared by boiling an ethanol solution of $RhCl_3$ or methoxyethanol solution of Na_3IrCl_6 with PPh_3 in presence of $NaBH_4$ and aq. $HCHO$ ²². Both the hydrido carbonyls are efficient catalysts for the hydrogenation and isomerization of alkenes^{9,17,295,296}. The Rh complex also serves as a hydroformylation and hydroacylation catalyst for alkenes²⁹⁷⁻²⁹⁹; the complex has a trigonal bipyramidal geometry with hydride and CO groups occupying the axial positions². Hydrido carbonyls $HRh(CO)L_3$ ($L=PEt_3, PBu_3^n, PMePh_2, PEt_2Ph$) have been synthesised by heating $RhCl_3$ with L in n-propanol³⁰⁰. Levison and Robinson¹⁶⁴ have studied the displacement of a PPh_3 ligand in $HM(CO)L_3$ by SO_2 group in ether to give $OM(CO)(SO_2)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3; \nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}=-/2050; \nu_{IrH/\nu_{CO}}=1965/2065$); this reverts back to the parent compound $HM(CO)L_3$ ($\nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}=2041/1918; \nu_{IrH/\nu_{CO}}=2125/1915$) on treatment with PPh_3 in benzene.

Yagupsky and Wilkinson³⁰¹ have described the preparation of the five-coordinate hydrido carbonyls $HfR(CO)_2L_2$ ($L=PEtPh_2; \nu_{IrH/\nu_{CO}}=2083/1962, 1915; \tau_H/J_{PH}=21.58 t/17.5$) by the $NaBH_4$ reduction of $IrCl(CO)L_2$ [$L=PPh_3, PEt_2Ph, P(C_6H_4F)_3$] in presence of CO. The Rh analog ($L=PPh_3$) is also known³⁰².

X-ray studies indicate a distorted trigonal bipyramidal configuration for the Ir complex ($L=PPh_3$) with the hydride and a PPh_3 group situated at the axial positions ($Ir-H=170; Ir-P=237.2, 237.7; Ir-CO=182.8, 186.3$ and $C-O=117.6, 121.7$ pm)³⁰³. A variety of five-coordinate complexes of the formulae $HfR(CO)(CF_3CO_2)_2L$, $HfR(CO)(\pi-CS_2)L_2$ ($L=PPh_3$) and $HfR(CO)_2L$ ($L=PEt_3, PPr_3^i, PBu_3, PPh_3, p\text{-tolyl}_3P$) have been synthesised³⁰⁴⁻³⁰⁶. Glockling and Wilbey³⁰⁷ suggest a trigonal bipyramidal configuration for the hydrido carbonyl $HfRCl(CO)(GePh_3)(PPh_3)$ ($\nu_{IrA/\nu_{CO}}=2083/1968; \tau_H/J_{PH}=18.5d/15.6$).

Hydrido carbonyls of Rh are relatively less stable than their Ir counterparts. Reddy and Leelamani³⁰⁸ have isolated octahedral complexes $HRhBr_2(CO)L_2$ [$L(\nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}})=PPh_3(2025/2055; cf. 2107/2049)^{309a}, AsPh_3(2080/2048), AsMePh_2(2035/2062), AsEtPh_2(2060/2040)$] by the oxidative addition of aq. HBr to $RhBr(CO)L_2$ in dichloromethane-ethanol. These complexes are not very stable and dissociate in dichloromethane solutions— $HRhBr_2(CO)L_2 \rightleftharpoons RhBr(CO)L_2 + HBr$. In a similar way, oxidative addition of HCl to $RhX(CO)L_2$ (in benzene/ether) occurs to give $HRhXCl(CO)L_2$ [$X/L=CF_3CF_2H/PPh_3; \nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}=2155/2090; \tau_H=22.6; X/L=Cl/PMe_3(2\text{-}MeOC_6H_4); \nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}(chloroform)=2090/2060; \tau_H/J_{RhH}/J_{PH}=23.5d/16.1/11.5$]^{309,310}. Isolation of the six-coordinate hydrido carbonyls of Rh(III) $HRhX_2(CO)(N-N)$ [$X/N-N(\nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}})=Cl, Br/bipy(2115/2060, 2080), Cl/phen(2117/2052, 2075), Br/phen(2110/2045, 2072)$] has been claimed by Kingston *et al*³¹¹. A cationic hydrido carbonyl [$HRhCl(CO)L_3$]⁺ ClO_4^- ($L=AsMePh_2; \nu_{RhH/\nu_{CO}}=2047/1967$) has been isolated by passing CO into an acetone-benzene solution of $HRhCl_3$ (Conf. I) in presence of sodium perchlorate (excess)³¹².

Iridium forms an extensive series of hydrido carbonyls of the type $HfRX_2(CO)L_2$ ($X=halogen, anionic$ ligand; $L=$ tertiary phosphine or arsine); several of these complexes are obtained in stereoisomeric forms

having structures VI and VII. Normally, the complexes of Conf. VI are obtained by (a) passing CO into a hot methoxyethanol solution of iridium salt (halide) and subsequently adding the ligand (tertiary phosphine or arsine) followed by the respective hydrohalic acid, and (b) oxidative addition of HX to *trans*- $IrX_2(CO)L_2$, while the complexes of Conf. VII are prepared by (a) displacement of L *trans* to H in $HfRX_2L_3$ (β ; Conf. II)

with $\text{CO}^{23,6}$, and (b) addition of CO to five-coordinate hydrides, $\text{HfR}_2(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ^{6,4}. The products have been characterised by IR and NMR spectral studies in addition to other physical and chemical methods. The complexes of Conf. VI undergo facile dehydrohalogenation on treatment with bases such as NaOMe, KOH and Pip [to yield $\text{IrX}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$], whereas the isomers of Conf. VII are resistant to such treatment^{1,7}.

Oxidative addition of silanes, germanes, areneselenols, alkyl/aryl thiols, dithio-phosphoric and -phosphinic acids, pentaborane etc., to Vaska's complex *trans*- $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) in a suitable solvent (e.g., benzene) results in the formation of octahedral hydrido carbonyl derivatives $\text{HfRCl}(\text{CO})(\text{Y})\text{L}_2$ [$\text{Y}=\text{SiH}_3, \text{SiH}_2\text{Cl}, \text{SiH}_2\text{Br}, \text{SiH}_2\text{I}, \text{GeH}_3, \text{GeH}_2\text{Cl}, \text{GeH}_2\text{Br}, \text{GeH}_2\text{I}, p\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Se}$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\delta\text{IrH}=2242/810$; $\nu\text{CO}/\nu\text{IrCl}=2028/270$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=19.52\text{t}/12$), $\text{R}_3(\text{R}=\text{Et}, \text{Pr}^i, \text{Bu}^n, \text{Cy}, \text{Ph}, p\text{-tolyl}$; $\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}\sim 2250/2040$), Ph_3PSS ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}=2185\text{m}/2035\text{vs}$), $(\text{PhO})_2\text{PSS}$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}=2205\text{m}/2040\text{vs}$); $\text{L}=\text{PMe}_3$; $\text{Y}=\text{B}_2\text{H}_5$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}=1978\text{s}/\Delta 082\text{s}$; $\nu\text{BH}/\delta\text{BH}=2573, 2555\text{m}/945$)^{21,1,22,188,248}. Treatment of $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PEt}_3$) with LiPh in ether followed by LiBr in ethanol leads to the formation of $\text{HfR}(\text{CO})(\text{Pn})\text{L}_2$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\delta\text{IrH}=2232\text{vs}/821\text{s}$; $\nu\text{CO}=2008\text{vs}$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=27.7\text{t}/12.7$)²⁰⁰. X-ray crystal structure suggests an octahedral configuration for the complex with P *trans* to P and Ph *trans* to $\text{CO}(\text{Ir}-\text{P}=232.7, 233.8$; $\text{Ir}-\text{Ph}=213$; $\text{Ir}-\text{C}=\text{O}=188$; $\text{C}-\text{O}=108\text{pm}$)³¹⁸. Lappert and Travers³¹⁴ have reported the

hydrido carbonyls of the type $\text{HfR}(\text{CO})(\text{SnR}_3)_2$ ($\text{X}/\text{L}=\text{halogen}/\text{PPh}_3$; $\text{R}=\text{Me}, \text{Ph}$). Addition of CO to the sixth coordination site (*trans* to H) of the hydride

$\text{HfR}\{\text{PBU}_2^t(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})\}_2$ in benzene takes place to give

$\text{HfR}(\text{CO})\{\text{PBU}_2^t(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O})\}_2$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}=2220/1995$)^{6,5}. A similar addition of CO to complexes of the type $\text{HMCl}(\text{PCP})(\text{PCPH}=\text{Bu}_2^t\text{PCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{PBU}_2^t)$ yields octahedral complexes $\text{HMCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PCP})(\nu\text{IrH}/\nu\text{CO}=2165/1985$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=17.6\text{t}/15$; Rh complex is formed as an intermediate; $\tau_{\text{H}}=17.5$)^{6,5}. Oxidation of $[\text{Ir}(\text{CN})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]\text{ClO}_4$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) in dichloromethane-ethanol with HClO_4 produces the cationic complex $[\text{HfR}(\text{CN})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\nu\text{IrH}/\delta\text{IrH}=2150\text{m}/820, 795\text{m}$; $\nu\text{CN}/\nu\text{CO}=2140\text{sh}/2055\text{vs}$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}=21.7\text{t}, 19.9\text{t}/16$)¹⁸⁶.

Peone and Vaska¹⁹⁰ have synthesised the perchlorate coordinated hydrido carbonyls $\text{HMCl}(\text{OCIO}_3)(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ and $\text{H}_2\text{M}(\text{OCIO}_3)(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) respectively by the oxidative addition of HCl and H_2 to $\text{M}(\text{OCIO}_3)(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$. Similarly, oxidative addition of silicon hydrides to $\text{HfR}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ produces $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{Y})(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{Y}=\text{SiCl}_3, \text{SiCl}_2\text{Me}, \text{SiMe}_3, \text{SiMe}_2\text{Ph}, \text{SiPh}_3$, etc.)²¹⁵. Glockling and Wilbey³⁰⁷ have also obtained similar type of dihydrides $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{GeR}_3)_2$ ($\text{R}=\text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Cl}$) in the oxidation-reduction of $\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ with two molecules of trialkyl

$\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$, tertiary phosphine; $\text{X}=\text{halogen}$, anionic ligand; $\text{Z}=\text{anionic ligand}$; $\text{R}=\text{alkyl}$, substituted alkyl group; $\text{R}^i=\text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Cl}$; $\sigma\text{-carb}=2\text{-H-1,2-B}_{10}\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}^-$; 7-R-1,7-B_{10}^- C_4H_{10} ; $\text{R}=\text{H}, \text{Me}, \text{Ph}$; $\text{Y}=\text{SiCH}_3, \text{GeR}_3, p\text{-MeC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Se}, \text{Ph}_3\text{PSS}, \text{B}_2\text{H}_5$ etc.

Scheme 22

germanes. Fawcett and Harrod^{21,6} have investigated the kinetics of the reactions $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3 + \text{Ph}_3\text{M}'\text{H} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{M}'\text{Ph}_3)\text{L}_2 + \text{L}$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$; $\text{M}' = \text{Si, Ge, Sn}$) in toluene/dichloromethane. Oxidative addition of H_2 (or D_2) to $\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\sigma\text{-carb})\text{L}_2$ ($\sigma\text{-carb} = 2\text{-H-1, 2-B}_{10}\text{C}_2\text{H}_{13}$; $7\text{-R-1,7-B}_{10}\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}$; $\text{R} = \text{H, Me, Ph}$; $\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2$) yields $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\sigma\text{-carb})\text{L}_2$; the dihydrido carbonyl forms stereoisomers depending on the solvent (polar/non-polar) used^{1,97}. Protonation of the hydrido carbonyl $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) with R_2PSSH ($\text{R} = \text{Ph, PhO}$) in benzene, or HF and Si in benzene-methanol leads to the formation of $[\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3]^+$; the crystal structure of which indicates an octahedral configuration (H atoms not located) with $\text{Ir-P} = 233.4, 234.5$ & 242.6 and $\text{Ir-CO} = 185 \text{ pm}^{1,21,317}$.

Hydrogenolysis of the dihydrido carbonyls $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{GeR}_3)\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) produces the trihydrido carbonyl $\text{H}_3\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ ⁹⁰⁷, which acts as a homogeneous hydrogenation catalyst²⁹⁶. Displacement of a molecule of hydrogen in H_2IrL_2 with CO also yields $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2$ (formed in solution; $\text{L} = \text{PEt}_2\text{Ph}$; $\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}}/J_{\text{HH}} = 20.79/16.5/4.8$ (H *trans* to H), $21.58/20.7$ (H *trans* to L) which readily loses H_2 to form $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\tau_{\text{H}}/J_{\text{PH}} = 21.57/24.9$)¹⁰⁷. $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3$ and $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) undergo oxidative addition with acetylides to give dihydrido acetylides complexes $\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{C} \equiv \text{CR})\text{L}_2$ ($\text{R} = \text{alkyl}$ or substituted alkyl). Likewise, on the oxidation of $\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\pi\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5)\text{L}_2$ with $\text{RC} \equiv \text{CH}$ six-coordinate hydrido carbonyls $\text{HIr}(\text{CO})(\sigma\text{-C}_3\text{H}_5)(\text{C} \equiv \text{CR})\text{L}_2$ are formed as intermediates²¹⁵. Protonation of $\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{CpL}_3$ in presence of NOPF_6 gives $[\text{HIr}(\text{CO})\text{CpL}_3]^+$ species²⁹⁴. Oxidative addition of H_2 to $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2]^+$ ions in acetone-methanol yields dihydrido dicarbonyl cations *cis*- $[\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\text{L}/\tau_{\text{H}} = \text{PPh}_3/19.8\text{t, PMePh}_2/20.4\text{t, PEtPh}_2/20.5\text{t, PEt}_2\text{Ph}/21.0\text{t, PET}_3/21.4\text{t, PCy}_3/21.5\text{t, PPr}_3/21.8\text{t, AsPh}_3/21.5$). The reaction is reversible and the parent compounds may be regenerated by the passage of CO into the dihydride in solution²²³. The cation $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\text{L} = \text{PMe}_2\text{Ph}$) also adds on HCl and H_2 oxidatively to form hexa-coordinate carbonyl cations $[\text{HIrCl}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3]^+$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{L}_3]^+$ respectively²²⁴. The dihydrido carbonyl cations of the latter type where H is *trans* to CO ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3, \text{PMePh}_2$) are also known^{223,205}. Similarly, oxidative addition of HCl

and H_2 to the cation $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})(\text{CN}(\text{Me})\text{C}(\text{Me})\text{CHS})\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$) yields the hydrido carbonyl carbene cations,

(iii) Palladium and Platinum

No hydrido carbonyl complex of Pd is known. A few four-coordinate hydrido carbonyl complexes of Pt(II) have been investigated, and almost all of them conform to the 16 e rule. However, a few halogeno hydrido carbonyls of Pt(IV) have also been prepared recently.

Tertiary phosphine or arsine hydrido carbonyls of Pd have not yet been isolated. The claim on the preparation of the four-coordinate anion $[\text{HPdCl}_2(\text{CO})]^-$ ($\nu\text{PdH}/\nu\text{CO} = 1960/1900$) by Kingston and Scollary²²⁴, by passing CO into an acidic solution of PdCl_2 in alcohol, has been shown to be incorrect by Goggin and Mink²²⁵, and the ion has been reformulated as $[\text{Pd}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{CO})_2]^{2-}$ on the basis of IR and PMR spectral results of the Pt analog. The anion, $[\text{HPtCl}_2(\text{CO})]^-$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{CO} = 2208/2070$; $\tau_{\text{vH}} = 25.12$) has been detected in dichloromethane solution of $[\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_4(\text{CO})_2]^{2-}$ treated with gaseous HCl.

A few four-coordinate cationic hydrido carbonyl complexes *trans*- $[\text{HPt}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]^+$ ($\text{L}/\nu\text{CO}$ & $\nu\text{PtH}/\tau_{\text{H}} = \text{AsEt}_3/2049$ & $2149/1.65$, $\text{PET}_3/2064$ & $2167/14.76$, $\text{PMePh}_2/2070$ & $2170/-$, $\text{PPh}_3/2087$ & $2188/-$) have been prepared by passing CO into an acetone solution of the parent hydride *trans*- HPtXL_2 ($\text{X} = \text{halogen}$) in presence of bulky anion such as ClO_4^- , BPh_4^- and PF_6^- as sodium salt. The deuterio analogs $[\text{DPt}(\text{CO})\text{L}_2]^+$

X = halogen, anionic ligand; Y = ClO_4 , BF_4 , BPh_4
 $\text{L} = \text{PPh}_3$, tertiary phosphine or arsine

Scheme 23

($L/\nu\text{CO}=\text{AsEt}_3/2092$, $\text{PEt}_3/2102$) have also been synthesised^{12,14,15}. The PPh_3 hydrido carbonyl ($\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{CO}=2170/2070$) formed starting from $[\text{Pt}(\text{N}_2\text{H})\text{L}_2]_2[\text{BF}_4]_2$ and CO, has been suggested to be an intermediate^{14,1}.

Action of CO and H_2 (under pressure in an autoclave) on $\text{HPt}(\text{SnCl}_3)_2$ ($\text{L}=\text{PPh}_3$) in benzene produces $\text{HPt}(\text{CO})(\text{SnCl}_3)_2$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{CO}=2165/2050$; $\nu\text{SnCl}=335,314,292$). The hydrido carbonyl, which may be four or five-coordinate, has been found to be selective hydroformylation catalyst for 1-pentene^{9,20}. Russian workers²¹ have isolated the $\text{Pt}(\text{IV})$, five- and six-coordinate dihydrido carbonyls $\text{H}_2\text{PtX}_2(\text{CO})$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{PtX}_3(\text{CO})]^-$ ($\text{X}=\text{halogen}$) by the oxidation of $\text{Pt}(\text{CO})_2$ with $\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ in hydrohalic acids. The complex $\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_2(\text{CO})$ ($\nu\text{PtH}/\nu\text{CO}=2125,2075/2125$) on deuteration forms $\text{D}_2\text{PtCl}_2(\text{CO})$ ($\nu\text{PtD}/\nu\text{CO}=1380,1465/2125$).

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